

Registers of constitutions. Designing a corpus for research on functional variation in German consti- tutional texts from 1871 onwards

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This master's thesis presents an investigation into functional and situational variation within historical legal documents. The research project consists of the design and construction of a corpus collecting foundational German legal documents belonging to the *constitutional paradigm*. Taking the different German constitutions as its basis, the *konkorp*-corpus aims for the documentation and annotation of both endo- and exogenous features within the texts. The goal is to offer a workable and searchable corpus allowing for granular and widespread research into both diachronic as well as situational-functional variation. After outlining the theoretical foundations in linguistics, constitutional law and history, a design of the multi-layered corpus architecture is sketched, followed by specific guidelines on how to annotate functional and situational parameters. Afterwards, a plethora of case studies provides insight into the structural make-up and feature distributions of the underlying documents and potential functional variation. The results of this statistical analysis will then be measured up against proposed hypotheses. Finally, basic problems in design and method will be highlighted.

1. Introduction: Linguistic research on law and the constitutional paradigm

The shared logics and themes across these domains—arrangements of law and fact, of priority and sequence, and of the real and the fictional—invite the language of reversibility, or multidirectionality: constitutions were modes of theory making, and, in reverse, concepts were order making. What is a constitution save a living theory of the state in question—the state distilled into abstract form, propositional form, the state on paper? (Wheatley 2023: 25)

Yet the historian is different: he or she makes use of texts solely as pieces of evidence, so as to determine a reality that lies behind the texts. More than all other textual exegetes, the historian thematizes a state of affairs that is in every case extra-textual, even if he or she only ever constitutes its reality by linguistic means. (Koselleck 2018: 58)

In modern legal frameworks, constitutions act as the foundational documents for their respective states. They convey basic normative ideas about the ways in which their societies are organized. This includes distinct notions about citizenship, basic rights, legal subjectivity and state organization, among others (Stein and Frank 2010: 2). However, it often remains unclear how these values are realized within constitutions, how they are institutionalized within societies, and ultimately, how they emerge from a historical perspective. The bearing language has on law has been a focal point of modern linguistic research for the past half century, with researchers working in different legal fields such as normative theories, lawmaking and jurisprudence. Since its inception in 1983, the Heidelberg Group has provided much work on German law and

its linguistic representation. In the 40 years that followed, the field of linguistics of law has proliferated to a significant degree, especially in the anglophone world. With the advance of corpus linguistics and computational methods, linguists and legal scholars have been able to process enormous amounts of legal data, from statutes to court documents to academic research. Pioneering work on the topic of constitutional linguistics comes from Carlson et al. (2015) and Livermore et al. (2016), both focusing on the U.S. Supreme Court of Justice. Recent examples of this kind of research on the German legal system arrived from Wendel et al. (2022) and Möllers et al. (2020), the first focusing on topic clusters of court proceedings of the German *Verfassungsgericht* ‘Federal Constitutional Court’ (FCC) and the second highlighting the canonization of certain FCC decisions within the legal literature. While all of these studies concern constitutional matters, they explore different focal points: *topics, canonization, style*, etc. The focus is often shifted away from concrete language use to statistical structures uncovered by processing enormous volumes of data. As a complement to this approach, I propose working on a smaller scale while focusing on a commonly overlooked aspect in legal linguistics: variation based on situational and functional considerations. This leads to the analysis of the constitutions within the framework set by register studies. Register as conventionalized context-dependent language use (Pescuma et al. 2023: 2) might elucidate emerging or evolving patterns in historical legal language use.

The goal of this thesis is the conduction of a small explorative study, aiming to lay the groundwork for extensive register analyses of the modern German constitutional archetype, starting systematically with the 1871 *Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* ‘Constitution of the German Empire’ (but including the failed *Paulskirchenverfassung*¹ ‘Constitution of St. Paul’s Church’ of 1848) and going all the way to the second constitution of the German Democratic Republic in 1968. The result of this thesis is the diachronic *konkorp*-corpus. A first base hypothesis can be formulated at this point: the constitutions of the German states share patterns of functional variation, which points to the existence of a constitutional register.

¹ The naming convention for constitutional documents will be as follows: proper names of constitution in composite form (e.g. *Paulskirchenverfassung, Grundgesetz, Reichsverfassung*) will be rendered in German, while the genitive constructions (e.g. *Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs*) will be translated after the first occurrence, either as a couplet with the respective state (as a proper name, i.e. Constitution of the German Empire) or with its year (i.e. constitution of 1871). In case of identical title, the year will also be provided (i.e. *Die Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* (1919)).

This approach mirrors certain developments in the historical sciences, where a growing number of historians explore the impact of written constitutions on state formation, ideology and identity, such as Natasha Wheatly in her analysis on early constitutional Central Europe in *The Life and Death of States* (2023). This foregrounding of discursive and communicative spaces in state conception serves as a suitable basis for attempting the formalization of both situational and functional aspects of constitutional documents. Instead of trying to explain changes in state conception using distributional patterns of isolated linguistic features alone, expanding the available context should enable easier tracking of continuities or discrepancies. Doing so will require careful annotation of the corpus. Given that the konkorp-corpus is based on historical documents, extrapolation of historically contingent contexts is extremely difficult (Koselleck 2018: 18; Lüdeling et al. 2022: 10). Besides the annotation of linguistic features (such as parts-of-speech), the project necessarily includes the mapping of legal and, more specifically, constitutional categories onto situational-functional variables.

In addition to the main hypothesis that individual constitutions show signs of a single register, a secondary hypothesis will also be investigated. The existence of multiple or parallel registers within certain text productions (Egbert & Mahlberg 2020; Egbert & Gracheva 2023) will be tested with regards to constitutional documents. Since constitutions bundle different, idiosyncratic functions (and even text types), it might be reasonable to assume that, e.g. basic rights and organizational norms represent different styles or even registers.

Because of the scope of full-scale register studies, this thesis limits itself to first explaining the underlying theoretical motivations of the project, followed by an outline of corpus design, construction and annotation. Statistical analysis of both structural and functional variation will be provided with case studies in the second half. And finally, a reevaluation of the research questions and hypotheses will be provided, after which problems and critical insights will close out this thesis.

2. Theoretical background

Before moving on to specific details of design and method, the necessary theoretical foundations will be expanded upon first. Due to the confluence of different research paradigms, the thesis is fundamentally interdisciplinary in its approach. It touches upon both legal as well as register linguistics, legal philosophy and constitution law,

and historical science. Modelling extra-linguistic components and variables can only be achieved through a synthesis of these respective fields.

2.1. Legal linguistics

As an investigation into the linguistics of constitutions, this thesis can be situated within the broader field of legal linguistics or forensic linguistics. The tradition of modern legal linguistics stretches back to the middle of the 20th century and finds its roots in both the philosophy of language and the philosophy of law. Due to the long histories and lasting influence of its progenitors, legal linguistics covers a broad range of topics within the fields of language and law, from normative theories to legal meaning making to the analysis of large volumes of judicial data. While the paradigm originated in the anglophone legal tradition, drawing on the works of legal-philosophical scholars such as HLA Hart, its German counterparts were established during the 70s and 80s, centering around the Heidelberg Group. A significant contributor is Friederich Müller, who broke ground in the second half of the 20th century by initially focusing his work on normative constitution, i.e. the structural logic binding legal norms (Müller 1966). From this vantage point, he launched investigations into the role language played in norm constitution. His theories will be elaborated upon in Section 2.3.2 due to their importance for the modelling of functional components.

While legal linguistics has its origins in the philosophies of law and language, much of the contemporary application of the discipline is centered on empirical analysis. With the onset of corpus linguistics and increasing computational capabilities available to researchers, it became possible to process huge amounts of data and explore distributional patterns contained therein (Gries 2020: 632). There is a focus on the analysis of legal terminology, achieved via comparison in large text collections, for example. Other subfields within the discipline are focused on modelling macrostructures within legal documents, others again analyze court proceedings and verdicts for statistical regularities. Important methodology fundamental to corpus linguistics like *keyword-in-context-search* (KWIC), analyzing multi-word units (MWU) or determining frequency and collocation patterns are central to the computational approach (Vogel 2017: 294-295). The combination of sophisticated algorithmic methods with surging computational capabilities laid the groundwork for the rising trend of topic or cluster modelling (Shadrova 2021). Rockmore et al. (2018), for example, have

analyzed huge amounts of data to generate topical clusters, categorizing constitutions based on topicality and theme.²

With regards to German research programs in the field, Friedemann Vogel has been especially active, mainly focusing on legal semantics and pragmatics (Vogel et al. 2019; Luth & Mattfeldt 2022). His work touches upon different aspects of language and law than his anglophone counterparts. In part, this can be explained by reference to the extremely statutory nature of much of German law³. The dimension of state conception has been investigated for Switzerland by Abegg & Bubenhofer (2016), again, primarily focusing on legal semantics. Investigation into the underlying constitutional documents, however, has been relatively sparse, perhaps due to the comparatively smaller sample size offered by constitutions. Furthermore, constitutions as subsets of legal documents deviate significantly from other forms such as court proceedings or even legislative texts.

In total, legal linguistics offer a variety of perspectives on the realm of law. And while explorations of constitutional law are not uncommon, the investigation of the field based on exogenous variables remains a niche. Still, the application of clustering methods can be understood as an attempt to trace the presence of extra-linguistic components through computational methods. Using these insights as the starting point, this thesis then aims to remedy some of these oversights by taking situational-functional variation into account from the onset.

2.2. Register linguistics

Over the years, many notionally similar yet distinct approaches to the research of registers have crystallized. The program was arguably launched through successive by Labov (1966), Halliday (1978) and Biber (1988). Central to this research paradigm was the importance of extra-linguistic components within text productions (both oral and written). As result of the multitude of approaches, there are now many different definitions of register within the context of Systemic Functional Linguistics (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014). Biber, for example variously refers to register as “linguistic variation associated with differences in use rather than group differences associated with the user” (1988: 33-34) or “culturally recognized categories of texts” (Biber et al.

² These methods rely on the so-called Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), whereby sets of word distributions are determined and labelled by topic and theme (Wendel et al. 2022).

³ As opposed to the system of common or case law commonly found in the English-speaking world.

2020: 585) Pescuma et al. (2023) define register as conventionalized language use depending on both extra- as well as endo-linguistic parameters, pointing to:

[...]processes [at the historical level often accompanied by sedentarism (vs. nomadism), state formation, evolution of ideology and religion, etc.] [that] manifest themselves in the situation-specific use of language, with interlocutors able to switch between varieties according to their distinct social roles and personae (which depend on situational-functional contexts). (Pescuma et al. 2023: 24)

Within the context of my research program, I remain closest to the working latter definition provided by Pescuma et al. (2023), focusing on a combination of exo- and endo-linguistic material. Followingly, basic elements of text production and communicative situations will be explained first, followed by a quantitative operationalization paradigm introduced by Biber (1988, 2009) and concluded by highlighting recent insights on the emergence of parallel registers within individual text types.

2.2.1. Elements of communicative and discursive situations

Since register studies focus on the on functional variation of language use, it first becomes necessary to understand what exactly is meant by functionality. When considering intra-individual language variation, for example, it is often difficult to ascertain which (contextual) parameters contribute to any observed variation. Discursive and communicative spaces are defined by production and reception, thus involving speakers and receivers and their relationship⁴. They are bound by concrete situational contexts like text type or genre. Channel determines the underlying medium of communication, i.e. whether any given text was written or produced orally. Communicative goals correspond to different realizations of linguistic material, etc. Early formalizations of these parameters include the *Field-Tenor-Mode* model (FTM), focusing on the qualities of *field* (the arena of communication, discursive subjects or topics), *tenor* (participants of communication, social relations between them) and *mode* (channels of communication) (Halliday and Matthiessen 2014: 54-56). However, application of the FTM-model is not universal and has to be amended depending on the specific use case. For this study, the model proves to be somewhat of an ill fit. It is, for example, incredibly difficult to accurately model the field of constitutional communication, since there is no clear bidirectional relationship between producer and receiver.

⁴ Examples are social rank or hierarchy, e.g. between authority figures and their addressees as in religious texts (Beier et al. 2023: 493).

Constitutions themselves are documents drafted and adopted by states through committees and convents and addressed to themselves. As such, there is no clear indication of how to apply the tenor category. As a result, this aspect of production has been modelled in a different fashion. Similar problems are encountered when taking stock of the other categories. Still, it is possible to formalize the unique discursive spaces of constitutions. Due to their explicit functionality within the legal system as expressed by constitutional norms, an alternative model for the parametrization of extra-linguistic material can be derived.

An added layer of difficulty is introduced by the reconstruction of historical contextual information. It is often extremely difficult to provide accurate judgements about concrete historical situations, ranging from information about speakers, goals, functions, etc. To a certain degree, these issues can be ignored within the proposed dataset. For one, our designation of speaker in the corpus remains constant, broadly defined as the state in both productive and receptive roles. Furthermore, constitutions, as mentioned above, are extremely functionalistic in their design, allowing for easier recourse to underlying communicative functions. And lastly, constitutions are highly structured text productions, divided into different sections both on a macro- as well as microstructural level. Since the documents within the corpus are derived from a broad legal tradition, these qualities are mostly shared by the individual documents, simplifying the modelling processes.

2.2.2. Multidimensional analysis of register

While earlier models of situational-functional variation were chiefly concerned with variation by way of exogenous influence, it was Biber's (1988) work that presented a quantified analysis of variation within the text. With the "multi-dimensional analysis" (MDA) Biber introduces quantificational models to measure texts according to dimensional scores, each highlighting individual characteristics of common registers (e.g. narrative or informational productions). Through use of the MDA, it became possible to bundle certain linguistic features and distinguish them as grouping features. If restricted to single registers, these features gain the status of "register marker" (Biber 2009: 823). These sets represent statistical groupings of variation between linguistic features, potentially enabling recourse to their underlying communicative situation. Looking at distributions of parts-of-speech like e.g. nominals and nominalizations, adjectives, infinitive verbs, adverbials, clauses, etc. will offer insights into conventionalized patterns of language use – patterns that could form parts of register inventories,

but don't necessarily have to. Distributional patterns alone cannot serve as primary evidence for discreet registers within texts. Only their realization in tandem with specific situational-functional variables and parameters allows researchers to draw conclusions with regards to the appearance of register phenomena.

The konkorp-corpus aims to allow for both kinds of register observations, the tabulation and calculation of frequency distributions, as well as the categorization of data according to its situational and functional boundaries. Searching for statistical patterns and clusters serves as the basis for testing the base hypothesis, investigating whether the individual documents show grouping features. Testing the corpus against already established dimensions can then help with determining potential register markers. Special attention will be paid to the dimension of informational (vs. involved) production, seeing as constitutions are highly functional and planned text productions. And due to constitutions being a prime example of texts produced by committee, the notion of distance will also be considered. The focus will ultimately be on clause structure, nominal and especially compound distributions, frequency of adjectives and verbal types.

2.2.3. Parallel registers in single text productions

A secondary aspect central to the project is the idea of parallel registers within singular texts. While the primary goal of the thesis is the construction of a corpus to allow for the investigation of a potential constitutional register, the work done by Egbert & Mahlberg (2020) and Egbert & Gracheva (2023) points to the possible emergence of multiple instances of conventionalized variation. The prime example of parallel register comes from functional variation in the genre of the novel. Different registers emerge depending on the functions of either a) auctorial narration and b) sections of dialogues signified by direct quotations. The latter sections of text turn out to be more closely aligned with spoken language production. In comparison, the narrative sections conform more clearly with the narrativity dimension D2 (Egbert & Mahlberg 2020: 92). While such a stark split cannot possibly be expected to surface within the konkorp-corpus⁵, there is some cause to believe that constitutions exhibit systematic variation dependent on different text functions. The classical liberal constitution is in parts defined by its paradigmatic combination of two distinct forms of law: a charter

⁵ Narration and dialogue commonly inhabit the diametrically opposed poles of written and oral production, although not exclusively (Ágel and Hennig 2006a; Biber 2009: 843).

of basic rights (civil rights) and organizational norms outlining the construction of the state. Based on this split, along which many constitutional commentaries are categorized, it might prove useful to rely on the situational-functional variables outlined within this thesis to test whether any significant variation can be detected (cf. Section 4.).

2.3. Constitutional Law

The central source for contextual information on constitutions and their underpinnings is, of course, the practice of constitutional law. In the following sections, fundamental aspects of the constitutional legal domain will be elaborated, explaining both the historical-political-legal background of its emergence, its basic tenets, as well as its place within the broader legal system of (modern) Germany. As a short working definition, we can say that constitutions represent the legal basis of states by enshrining fundamental principles regarding state construction and conduct (Stein and Frank 2010: 2; Koriath 2023: 2). Legitimacy of the state is, at least formally, derived from the constitution (Hermes 1988: 35).

2.3.1. Basics of constitutional law and its development

The constitutional variant at the center of this thesis, the classical liberal archetype, is a fundamentally modern development. Written (or codified) state documents have existed for millennia, among them such examples as the Magna Charta (1215) or the *Tübinger Vertrag in Württemberg* ‘Treaty of Tübingen’ (1514) (Scheuner 1978: 171). Only with the advent of early Modernity and the Enlightenment have text types containing the hallmarks of the modern constitutional form surfaced. From the second half of the 18th century onwards, written constitutions cementing both democratic and republican principles have proliferated, major shocks and influence arriving from the successful revolutions and constitutional moments in both the United States of America (1787) and France (1791) (Scheuner 1978: 172). The modern constitutional form then represents novel developments within history, such as the repudiation of the aristocratic and absolutist political systems of organization (Rolin 2020: 255). From the starting points in both Europe and the Americas, the constitutional form had spread all over the world. Adoption in the parts of Europe that were still dominated by the imperial order like Austria-Hungary, Prussia or Russia was comparatively slow and really only set in during the second half of the 19th century (Rolin 2020: 253-254).

Given this history, it becomes important to highlight the influence that Enlightenment era political-philosophical thought had on the development of key pillars of the constitutional order. Democratic fundamentals like the tripartite separation of powers, for example, were in part derived from Montesquieu's writings in *Spirit of the Law* (1748) (Korioth 2023: 110). Other elements such as the accountability towards its body politic (the political subjects) were pioneered by Jean-Jacque Rousseau, while the theorizing on the role of state government, or the hegemon, most notably came from Thomas Hobbes' *Leviathan* (1651) (Korioth 2023: 103, 110). A second important feature of the constitutional form is the inclusion of a basic or civil rights charter. While the definition of basic rights for sovereign subjects had been an element of state projects before the onset of the enlightenment (e.g. Magna Chara), it is through the recontextualization of politic subjects (of the estate systems) as part of a constitutive citizenry that centrally enshrined basic rights have gained salience (Manssen 2024: 3).

In the modern or contemporary form of constitutions, particularly within the German legal systems, there are two distinct parts to the constitutional body. On the one hand, constitutions outline basic rights granted (or conferred) to its citizenry, the *Grundrechte* 'basic rights', and, on the other, constitutions formulate the base principles of state organization. An example of the former is freedom of the press (e.g. Art. 5 Abs. 1 GG) and of the latter the definition of the parliament (e.g. Art. 23 DRV)⁶. This includes both procedural and functional statutes, denoting how basic structures of the state are organized⁷, which functions they exhibit and how certain governmental bodies are established or removed. There are additional principles outlining transitory periods (*Übergangsbestimmungen* 'transit terms'). While notionally part of organizational principles, these often resist easy categorization. Another novel part of many present-day constitutions are hierarchical or integrative principles with regards to supra- and international institutions, such as the integration into a European federation in the case of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany (e.g. Art. 23 GG).

⁶ Constitutional examples deviate from the citation style employed throughout. They will be referenced according to widespread jurisprudential practice. Citations will include a reference to the concrete norm (articles, paragraphs, sentences) and conventionalized abbreviations for the respective documents (e.g. Art. 1 Abs. 2 S. 3 GG). The abbreviations are as follows: Paulskirchenverfassung (no abbr.), Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs 1871 (Deutsche Reichsverfassung, DRV), Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs 1919 (Weimarer Reichsverfassung, WRV), Grundgesetz der Bundesrepublik Deutschland (GG), Verfassung der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik 1949, 1968 (DDR 49, 68).

⁷ Such structures can be state territory, governmental bodies, the judiciary, etc.

Lastly, constitutional law forms the basis of legal systems. Its application and legitimacy are often adjudicated by a constitutional or supreme court. Basic rights project primacy towards all other areas of the law, necessitating either conformity or specification by specific statutes. Within the structure of the German legal system, constitutional law is a subset of public law (as opposed to private law). It constitutes a unity with regulatory norms outside of constitutions (e.g. *Bundeswahlgesetz* ‘federal election law’) to form the area of state law, wherein all manners of the states are outlined or regulated (Stein and Frank 2010: 12-13). Constitutional and state law is special in the sense that the state not only takes up the role of producer and issuer of law, but also the role of its addressee. Overall, the basic function of constitutions can be summed as both containing the structuring principles of the state and its source of legitimacy.

2.3.2. Normative theories as basis for formalization of functional qualities

The most important prerequisite to the formalization of extra-linguistic material is the investigation of the functional space at the core of constitutional texts. It may be obvious, even plainly so, that constitutions are constitutive with respect to their overarching state structures. Yet at this point, it remains unclear how the textual production of constitutions translates to state power and legitimacy. Thus, it becomes integral to a theory of constitutional functions to examine the smallest (semantic) unit of legal meaning making: the norm. Norms essentially represent the basis of the legal system as tenets enforced by state power⁸. They both de- and prescribe either socially desired or undesired behaviors (Sunstein 1996: 11). There are many theories of how these behaviors are encouraged or incited, some of which will be more closely touched upon in Section 5.2. In the sense that legal norms regulate social behaviors, they represent a subset of social norms per se. Legal norms, especially as statutes, can be seen as formalizations of social norms in their own right. Of course, there is considerable leeway in both interpretation and adjudication of legal norms. The transposition of the (social) norm into a codified, propositional form is often incapable of fully capturing all of its unique qualities, retaining degrees of ambiguity.

⁸ State power as state authority qua holding the monopoly on violence vis-à-vis legitimacy via recognition (Hart 2012: 100-101).

Structurally, the norm can be split into different parts. For this thesis, I have chosen to highlight an approach championed by Friedrich Müller. In his 1966 dissertation *Normstruktur und Normativität*, Müller introduces a binary structure of the legal norm, one part constituting a *Normbereich* ‘normative area’ and the other the so-called *Normprogramm* ‘normative program’ (Müller 1966: 184-185). This split can be likened to situational-functional operationalizations often found in register analyses. The norm area fundamentally points to specific situational paradigms, foregrounding a kind of socially contingent topicality (or situationality). They circumscribe the total area of applicability of any given norm. The norm program, on the other hand, outlines the concrete functional thrust of the legal norm, containing its instructive elements of legal application. The norm program itself is formulated with legal subjects in mind and mediates social conflicts in both spheres of the law, i.e. the public sphere (relations between the state and itself) and the private sphere (the state and its citizens) (Müller 1966: 188; Stein and Frank 2010: 217).

With the norm structured into broad situational and functional components, the question shifts to its concrete effects on the world, i.e. the question of how social meaning is generated. There are a number of theories within the realm of philosophy of language that try to approximate the mechanisms through which norms enact their meaning. Robert. M Brandom of the Pittsburg School of pragmatism highlights key functions of norms with regards to their “discursive commitment” (Brandom 2001: 159). One function can be described as enabling assertions, while the other enables inferences. Assertions base themselves on *deontic statuses*, i.e. commitments to knowledge claims. On the other hand, *deontic attitudes* rest on the notion of attribution, judging or sanctioning behaviors on basis of their perceived relation to statuses (Brandom 2001: 166). Explicit assertive material then becomes the basis for inferential content. This conceptualization of norms can be relayed back to legal philosophy and the so-called *imperative theory*. A remnant of the purely punitive theory of the hegemon, imperative theory posits that legitimacy of all legal norms is achieved through the implicit threat of sanctions expressed by state authority (Kniffka 2008: 163). The theory was amended on several fronts, with HLA Hart contributing the idea that there are legal norms that do not necessarily exhibit the same characteristics. These can be labeled as “secondary rules” as opposed to the punitive “primary rules” (Hart 2012: 96). Much like the split between assertion and inference (or normative status and normative attitude), the two types of legal norms embody two different functions: knowledge claims which assert or establish certain facts and attitudes derived on basis of inference from statuses. As such, we can refer to the two primary types of norms

within the context of this thesis as either *constitutive norms* or *prescriptive norms*. Within the legal realm, the constitutive norm sets the base principles of conduct. It establishes the framework and fundamental procedures by which prescriptive norms can be enacted, and more importantly, adhered to. Thus, it functions as a generator of legal facts (Wiener 2011: 40) (cf. Section 5.2). With regards to the research project at hand, it's possible to posit a first kind of formalization of functional content: the individual norms will either be categorized as constitutive or prescriptive, pointing to their discursive functions in establishing facts or engendering and limiting behaviors.

This notion of communicative functionality is then reintegrated into the framework of Müller's normative theory. Taking a somewhat abstract view of the *normative program*, the functional space will be described by these assertive and inferential paradigms. The notion of *normative area*, however, is modelled on two other factors. The directionality of norms describes the direction of conflict mediation within broader society, either mediating between the state and itself or the state and its subjects. The second layer of normative area is given by reference to the normative type as either basic right or state organizational norm. The exact details of the formalization process for these functional considerations will be given in Sections 3.3.2 and 3.4.

2.4. Historical science

The last discipline touched by this thesis is the science of history. As the project is diachronic in nature, it becomes necessary to highlight factors influencing both the research project as a whole, as well as individual decisions on the level of annotation and study design. The general methods of history and central historical ideas of this thesis will be discussed as a first step. In Section 2.4.2., concrete details of historical developments will be discussed in order to show their influence on the annotation process. This includes a short summary of the historical context surrounding the individual states whose constitutions serve as the basis for the konkorp-corpus.

2.4.1. Basic methods and concepts

The basic method of the historical discipline is extensive work with sources. Within the context of this thesis, the importance of careful source selection is obvious. Since both legal-theoretical as well as historical literature directly influence decisions made during the design stage, it becomes paramount to have an adequate overview of the available sources. The situational-functional annotation aims to synthesize different

fields of research (historical, legal/constitutional, discursive). As such, the sources include both broad histories of state development provided by Osterhammel (2010), Clark (2019) and Kocka (2021), as well as literature on the historical development of the German constitutional form (Scheuner 1978; Kotulla 2008; Koriath 2023). One particular school of thought that has influenced the development of the research questions is the French Annales school. Spearheaded during the late 60s and 70s by French historian Fernand Braudel, the Annales school is characterized by their extremely detailed and longitudinal approach to the analysis of historical periods, exemplified by the concept of the *longue durée* (Braudel 1980: 25). The *longue durée* describes a historical method that places importance on the slow development of historical structures during extremely long periods of time⁹. The notion of the *longue durée* is central to the thesis presented here. While the time span covered by the texts is only slightly larger than a century (1849-1968), the “constitutional moment” can be conceptualized as both reaching further back to its beginnings in France and the United States and stretching forward to the present day¹⁰. Compared to other long-form historical periodizations such as those of the long 19th century¹¹, the core period covered by the constitutional texts represents a kind of interregnum, not cleanly overlapping with either the 18th or the 19th century. Still, the idea that the successive constitutions form a kind of continuum structuring large periods of German (legal) history, informed the approach to the design of a diachronic corpus focused on contextual variation. Exploring the hypothesis that it is possible to approximate a singular constitutional register presents a kind of formalization of the method of *longue durée*.

2.4.2. The history of German state formation in the constitutional age

Because the corpus contains situational variables based on historical extrapolation, it is necessary to summarize the development of the constitutional form, as well as some key information about the successive German states relevant to the thesis. They are: the abortive German Empire in 1849, the German Empire in 1871, the German Empire in 1919¹², the Federal Republic of Germany and the Democratic Republic of Germany (both from 1949 onwards). As mentioned by Scheuner (1978: 172), the American and

⁹ Braudel himself is famous for his histories of the mercantilist Mediterranean and the early modern French state (Stoianovich 1976: 66).

¹⁰ Since the constitution of the FRG is still in place.

¹¹ See the work of Eric Hobsbawm or Perry Anderson, for example.

¹² Commonly referred to as the Weimar Republic.

French constitutional precedents set the standard for the constitutional form that was to be emulated across the nascent nation states of Europe during much of the 19th century. Before a unified German state could give itself a constitution, the predecessor state formations were constituted chiefly by local documents like *Deutsche Bundesakte* ‘Constitution of the German Confederation’ (1815), enacted in the aftermath of the Napoleonic wars. The *Bundesakte* reordered the sovereignty of the German principalities (Kotulla 2008: 327-328). It is within the context of the absolutist restoration in the first half of the 19th century that the first proper constitutional project was launched within the HRE. After the revolutionary March of 1848, the newly constituted German parliament in Frankfurt drafted the so-called *Paulskirchenverfassung*, thereby creating the first German constitution. The *Paulskirchenverfassung* included not only articles of state organization but also a basic rights charter, the abolishment of the estate system and many archaic holdovers of the absolutist era, as well as the devolution of powers to individual branches of government (Korioth 2023: 183). The constitution was drafted in 1848-1849 and parts of it were ratified on March 28th 1849. Ultimately, the revolutionary moment was suppressed before the *Paulskirchenverfassung* could be established as the constitutional foundation (Korioth 2023: 184, 187). The *Paulskirchenverfassung* described a system containing free and secret elections (of the male population above 25), a representative parliament and federal representation. As stated before, the estate system was formally abolished. The monarchical system was retained, however. Conclusively, the German proto-state was a constitutional monarchy with some degree of federal autonomy (Kotulla 2008: 186-187).

After the monarchical restoration following the March Revolution, the Prussian state centralized its power in the following decades, ultimately engaging in multiple wars during the 1860s, first against the Danish Kingdom in 1864, then against the alliance of Austria-Hungary and the *Deutscher Bund* ‘German Confederation’ in 1866 and lastly against France in 1870/1871 (Clark 2019: 159; Kocka 2021: 193-194). The victory of the Prussian state ended in the founding of the first unified German state, the German Empire (*Deutsches Reich*). During the wars, the Prussian central state established multiple constitutional documents, first the *Verfassung des Norddeutschen Bunds* ‘North German Constitution’ in 1867, then the *Verfassung des Deutschen Bunds* ‘Constitution of the German Federation’ in 1870 and finally, the *Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* ‘Constitution of the German Empire’, declared on April 16th 1871 (Korioth 2023: 203). Since each of these constitutions outlined confederacies of states with relatively high federal autonomy, the constitutions were centered around establishing the organizational parameters of central authority (Korioth 2023: 206-207).

The definition of basic rights was left to the auspices of the individual member states and their respective constitutions. While the state formations of the emergent German Empire came about as result of successive wars, the damage done to the underlying political-economic structure of the Prussian central state was somewhat negligible, retaining many of its previous features, such as the constitutional paradigm set by 1867 constitution (Kotulla 2008: 526) or the monarchical structure of the previous Prussian state (Clark 2019: 156-157). Since the successive constitutions were relatively similar in content and form, only the final constitution of 1871 is included within the corpus. It describes a system of unified, autonomous federal states. The monarchy is retained and upgraded to an imperial form. Elections are fair and free and limited to adolescent males of age 25 and upwards. The system is a constitutional monarchy with democratic features and high federal autonomy.

Following the First World War, the erstwhile German Empire and its monarchy was toppled during the revolutionary autumn of 1918/1919. On August 11th 1919, the constitution of the newly constituted German Empire was declared. The abolition of the monarchy and flight of Emperor Wilhelm II. resulted in the “decapitation of the state” (Clark 2019: 165). Additional constraints came as a result of the treaty of Versailles, severely limiting German economic capabilities by imposing both reparations and annexing the industrially powerhouse of Alsace-Lorraine (Kotulla 2008: 589). Much of the legal system and elite political structures were upheld, however. Parties and laws established during the Kaiserreich like the SPD (Social Democratic Party) and the *Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch* ‘Civil Law Code’ (1900) were carried over from the previous system. Similarly, significant parts of the administrative state were retained, although subordinated to the new democratically legitimated authority (Clark 2019: 166), while chancellor Friedrich Ebert appealed to elements of continuity in law and military affairs (Korioth 2023: 247). The constitution introduced a new basic rights charter in parts modeled on the Paulskirchenverfassung, expanded democratic institutions and safeguards, as well as irrevocably abolishing the monarchy.¹³ The autonomy of the federal states was lowered to a significant degree by unitary decision of the *Nationalversammlung* ‘national assembly’, resulting in the subordination of the states to the central authority of the new Empire (Kotulla 2008: 589-590). The

¹³ Because of the binary formalization of a process category, there was significant difficulty in aligning the Weimar Republic to one or the other value. Ultimately, the decision was made in favor of the *transition* value (cf. Section 4.3., 9.1.).

constitution therefore describes a constitutional federal republic, with low federal autonomy. Men over the age of 20 were electable in free and fair elections.

The next set of constitutions were both adopted in 1949, following the occupation of Germany in the aftermath of the Second World War and the fall of the Nazi Regime. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany was declared first on May 23rd 1949. It returned to a system of constitutional, parliamentary republicanism with low federal autonomy, building on both the Paulskirchenverfassung and the constitution of the Weimar Republic (Korioth 2023: 388). Democratic principles were strengthened to a significant degree, introducing the *Demokratieprinzipien* ‘democratic principles’ (e.g. Art. 20 GG). The basic rights were enshrined in the first part of the constitution, anchored to the *Basisgrundrecht* ‘basic right’ outlined in Article 1 (e.g. *Menschenwürde* ‘human dignity’). The emergence of the state can be described as state building, since much of the economic capital was destroyed during the invasion of Nazi Germany during 1941-1945. While certain elements of previous state structure were resuscitated, including parties, laws and federal structures, the political system nevertheless represented a significant departure from its previous form (Korioth 2023: 368-371).

A similar set of political and economic circumstances laid the basis for the constitution of the German Democratic Republic. A successor state built on the former Soviet occupation zone, the initial German Democratic Republic was established on October 7th 1949. In its first instance, the constitution of the GDR similarly describes a constitutional federal republic with parliamentary representation of nominally free and fair elections (Korioth 2023: 402-404). Akin to the interpretation of the founding of the FRG as project of state building, the same can be said for the constitution of the GDR in 1949 due to the complete overhaul of the older political system.

The same cannot be said for its successor constitution introduced April 4th 1968. After the centralization of power within the Socialist Unitary Party (*Sozialistische Einheitspartei, SED*) and the central committee (*Zentralkomitee*), the state entered a phase of unitary party statism. Simultaneously with power centralization on the party level, the federal division of 1949 was abolished in 1958 (Korioth 2023: 405). Basic civil rights, such as voting rights, etc., were retained within the constitutions, despite their contested implementation. Several other civil rights based on “socialist” principles were also introduced, such as constitutional protections and duties for women, workers and unions (Korioth 2023: 410-411). The actual constitution is preceded by a section outlining basic state principles, describing the socialist commitments of the

GDR¹⁴. While the state received a new structure, much of the political economy remained the same. As such, the constitution of 1968 occurred under a process of state transition. The constitution of 1968 was followed by a second amendment in 1974. Since much of the character of the 1968 constitution was retained, only the first is included within the corpus.

It should be noted that the corpus does not include representative constitutional or state law documents from the Third Reich. The entire edifice of German constitutional law was dismantled during the early years of the Nazi regime, using the so-called *Reichsermächtigungsgesetze* ‘Enabling Act’ (Korioth 2023: 325). While it could be argued that there were certain bills of law that exhibit characteristics of state law, I have chosen not to include those due to a) their disparate nature; rudimentary state law was established via a series of different bills, each tackling different aspects of its implementation, making the case for a unified “constitutional” project difficult; and b) the bills containing elements of state law are often extremely short¹⁵. Despite small fluctuations of text lengths in the konkorp-corpus, the documents from the Third Reich would still have been dwarfed by even the shortest documents. As such, their inclusion would have been rendered useless and at worst, counterproductive to balanced statistical extrapolation.

3. Methodology

In the following section, I will quickly sketch the basic methods employed in the central task of this thesis program, the design and construction of a *constitutional corpus*. After outlining the basic research questions that motivate the program, the steps of text selection, data collection and processing, design of a functioning workflow, and, ultimately, the annotation of the text documents will be summarized. Guidelines will present a formalized approach to the annotation process, thereby allowing reproduction and modification of the corpus.

¹⁴ Such as the alliance with the Soviet Union and repudiation of U.S. imperialism (Präambel, DDRV 1968).

¹⁵ Examples are the 1933 Ermächtigungsgesetz (Enabling Act) and Gleichschaltungsgesetze (Laws on the Coordination of the States with the Reich).

3.1. Research questions

One of the goals of this thesis is to narrow down the research of constitutional linguistics to one specific paradigm. Due to the successive historical developments within the German state¹⁶, there are multiple individual constitutional texts that can be compared with and against each other. This offers the advantage of continuity, in the sense that the comparative work can be understood to remain within the realm of the German legal systems in the broadest sense¹⁷. An added benefit is the use of the same vernacular (High German) and even legal language, allowing not only for easier cross-document but also cross-norm comparisons. The idea of continuity then serves as the basis for the central research question and the motivating force behind the thesis: is it possible to define a constitutional register across the constitutive documents of the various modern German nation states? And if so, how would the necessary corpus be designed? Which texts must be included, how are they collected, how represented? Which annotations are necessary to capture the situational-functional variation inherent to register phenomena, etc.? The construction of the konkorp-corpus aims to answer these questions, while allowing its users to engage with German constitutions in a more interactive fashion. Connecting the tokenized constitutional texts with specific linguistic and exogenous annotations lays the basis for the definition of necessary thresholds to satisfy the conditions for categorization as a unique register.

The second major research question revolves around the observation of multiple registers within individual text types (Egbert & Mahlberg 2020). While constitutions serve as the foundational legal frameworks for their respective states, they nevertheless combine different functional and situational paradigms, most clearly observable in the split between basic (citizen) rights and the description of state construction. Since both paradigms serve different cogent purposes, it would be prudent to structure the annotation in such a way as to allow for extensive testing of any possible binary variation. As such, we can formulate two base hypotheses:

H₁: There is a contiguous register in the modern German constitutional archetype.

H₂: There are parallel styles or registers running through constitutions based on legal area.

¹⁶ *Deutschland* 'Germany' here as the term for all state formations from 1849 onwards.

¹⁷ Carried on by lineages of lawmakers, parties, politicians, legal traditions, etc.

Altogether, the research program explored within this thesis can be described as laying the basis for investigations into *intra*-textual (hypothesis 1) and *inter*-textual (hypothesis 2) variation dependent on either situational or functional considerations.

3.2. Data collection and corpus design

3.2.1. Text selection

The first step in the construction of the konkorp-corpus was *text selection*. Initially, a decision needed to be made regarding the scope of the corpus. Since constitutional history reaches farther back than the Paulskirchenverfassung, older documents were also considered for the thesis. In the lineages of the German state, there's been a variety of different documents that partly exhibit similar characteristics as modern constitutions. These types range from basic laws or rights, political contracts outlining sovereignty, peace treaties to historically contingent hybrid forms such as the political contracts like the *Goldene Bulle* 'Golden Bull' (Korioth 2023: 33) or the *Wahlkapitulation* 'electoral capitulation' of Karl V. (Kotulla 2008: 30) between the 14th and 16th centuries. These choices were quickly discarded due to both scope and inconsistency in text type. The focus then shifted to the modern constitutional paradigm, which in Germany was ushered in by the Paulskirchenverfassung in 1849. Consequently, the texts that were selected for the konkorp-corpus are: the *Paulskirchenverfassung* (1849), the *Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* 'Constitution of the German Empire' (German Empire, 1871), the *Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* 'Constitution of the German Empire' (Weimar Republic, 1919), the *Grundgesetz* 'Basic Law' (1949) and the *Verfassung der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik* 'Constitution of the German Democratic Republic' in 1949 and 1968. Exact details of the texts can be found in the documentation of the sub-corpora in the Appendix (9.1.).

3.2.2. Multi-layer corpus design and data processing

After conducting text selection, the exact design of the corpus structure was considered. Since one of the initial goals of the thesis was the investigation of a confluence of different factors, it quickly became clear that the corpus had to be multi-layered in nature (Odebrecht et al. 2017: 698-699; Zeldes 2020: 21-23). This meant that information would be stored in different to-be-annotated layers, which correspond with

each other, thereby constituting multiple instances of value pairs. Since the constitutions contain various structural elements outlining individual subunits of text, the corpus had to contain multiple layers consisting of spans, i.e. denoting and corresponding with entire sequences of tokens. These spans correspond to various structural components of the constitutions, such as chapters, sections and even the norm. The system of spans allowed for a reproduction of the structural hierarchy of constitutional documents with token sequences corresponding to sentences, paragraphs and articles, which in turn corresponded to sub-sections, etc. The following table (Table 1) illustrates a paradigmatic annotation of the third paragraph of Article 3 of the Grundgesetz (Art. 3 Abs. 3 GG), showing its different segmentations (token layer **word**) and annotation levels. The schematization highlights the underlying logic of the annotation. Spans are denoting either textual (tiers **genre** and **topic**) or normative belonging (tiers **form**, **type**, **direction**). Each subset of layers is anchored to different base layers, linguistic features to the token or **word** layer, normative features to the **paragraph** layer, situational features to the sectional layers and metadata to entire documents.

Word:	w1 w2 w3 w4 w5 w6 w7 w8 w9	w10 w11 w12 w13 w14 w15 w16
Comp:		
Clause:	Main	Main
List:		
Sent:	Satz 1	Satz 2
Paragraph:	Abs. 3	
Article:	Art. 3	
Form:	konstitutiv	
Type:	Grundrecht	
Direction:	Öffentlich	
Genre:	Grundrecht	
Topic:	Religion	
Metadata		
System:	Föderale Republik	
Trans:	building	

Table 1: Annotation scheme showing an exemplary annotation of Art. 4, Abs. 3 GG; values in column 1 corresponding to tier names. The amount of tokens is symbolic as the entire sequence would not have fit.

The texts themselves exist in digital form and are under public domain due to German copyright law on published legislative documents (§ 5 Abs. 1, UrhG). Additionally, the official printed versions initially released in the respective law gazettes were included for review and cross reference. The text documents were converted to the .txt-file format and, in a preliminary step, normalized for simplification. Since the digital versions of the documents were not formatted uniformly, the documents were first modified to match a singular formatting convention. Most glaringly were the differences in denoting sections, articles and paragraphs, with different documents employing either rounded, squared or no brackets at all for numbering paragraphs¹⁸. The ordinals denoting articles were similarly followed by either punctuation marks or led directly to the norm text. Accordingly, these different formatting choices were unified out of pragmatic considerations: presenting the texts within the corpus in a uniform

¹⁸ e.g. §1 [2] (§1, Abs. 2, Paulskirchenverfassung) vs. Art. 15 (1) (Art. 15 Abs. 1 WRV)

fashion. Of course, modifying original documents is a difficult choice in corpus construction. However, the idiosyncratic formatting decisions are the result of different representations of the documents. The underlying structures reflect a unified jurisprudential practice that is carried across constitutions (Rüthers et al. 2021: 400). The decision was made for the token *Artikel* to be followed by its corresponding number, which in turn is followed by the bracketed paragraph number. Despite these changes, it should be noted that I have abstained from changing numbering conventions employed with regards to the macrostructural sections of the text. In the constitution of the German Democratic Republic of 1949, for example, the chapters are numbered via capital letters (A., B. , C. , etc.), while the orthodox numeral format is used in the constitutions of 1871 and 1849. Since these chapter titles appear uniformly within printed editions of the respective texts, modification was unnecessary.

The edited .txt-files were then tokenized and automatically tagged for their parts-of-speech using the software TreeTagger 3.3.2. (Schmid 1994)¹⁹. Since the multi-layer architecture of the konkorp-corpus is in parts defined by its large text spans, the decision was made to use Microsoft's tabulation software Excel for the annotation of the texts. The first step after importation into Excel was the normalization of the base token layer. Since the constitutional documents reach back as far as 1849, there were considerable differences in orthographic representations²⁰. Examples for the deviation in writing standards can be found within the annotation guidelines (Section 3.4.). After normalization, the files were reconverted into plain text files. This was done in order to re-tag and re-lemmatize the documents with TreeTagger. Certain orthographic conventions have regularly been tagged incorrectly during the first application of the software, which is why a second iteration proved necessary and useful. The final TreeTagger-output was then reimported into Excel for correction and annotation. The next step consisted of a manual review of the **part-of-speech** layer and the **lemma** layer. Afterwards, the tables were annotated using the guidelines outlined below, highlighting specific linguistic features (clauses, compounds and lists), the structural make-up of the texts (sections, articles, paragraphs, etc.), as well as situational-functional variables (**direction**, **type**, **form**). These annotations were reviewed in multiple stages (from pre-tokenized test annotations to the final review of the entire corpus). The conversion software Annatto (Krause & Klotz 2023) was then used to

¹⁹ The software employs the *Stuttgart-Tübingen-Tagset* (Schiller et al. 1999).

²⁰ The first two documents within the corpus were formulated before the widespread standardization of the High German vernacular.

convert the individual and disparate Excel-files into a single corpus in the graphANNIS-format, to be used in the graphical search interface ANNIS (Krause & Zeldes 2016). The Annatto conversion was done using a workflow file, which was written in the TOML-format²¹. This allowed for concrete specification of the importer module, including failure checking the graph operation²², as well as of the exporting process, including modification of the visual representation. For the visual representation within ANNIS, the individual layers were grouped according to category into linguistic, structural and functional-situational layers. The result of an exemplary search prompt in ANNIS can be seen in the illustration (Fig. 1) below. Overall, the konkorp-corpus contains six documents and 60607 tokens in total.

The screenshot shows the ANNIS interface for a search prompt. It is divided into several sections: 'article', 'norm', 'word', 'annotation', 'structure', and 'register'.

article: Art. 20, Art. 21

norm: verantwortungsbewusst, teilzunehmen, Artikel, 21, (1), Jeder, Bürger, der, Deutschen, Demokratischen, Republik, hat, das, Recht, das, politische

word: verantwortungsbewußt, teilzunehmen, Artikel, 21, (1), Jeder, Bürger, der, Deutschen, Demokratischen, Republik, hat, das, Recht, das, politische

annotation: main, sub

structure: genre: Grundrechte, section_1: Teil 2, section_2: Abschnitt 1, topic: Basis

register: article: Art. 20, Art. 21; paragraph: Abs. 3, Abs. 1; sent: Satz 2, Satz 1; dir: öffentlich, öffentlich; type: grundrecht, grundrecht; form: konstitutiv, konstitutiv

Fig. 1: ANNIS view of a search prompt (Appendix 9.2.) with all categories (linguistic, structural and register) displayed.

3.3. Annotation of data

The following section represents the core of the corpus construction. The annotation layers will be described regarding their underlying motivation and structure. The categories can be broadly defined as *linguistic* variables, *register* variables and *metadata*,

²¹ Included in the Appendix in Section 9.2.

²² The failure check examines whether the corpus is fully searchable on the basis of regular expressions.

with the register categories being split into the subsets of *structural* variables and *situational-functional* variables.

3.3.1. Linguistic variables

The first categories of variables are a set of linguistic annotations. Since register as a phenomenon describes different conventions of language use, any apparent variation will be reflected in linguistic surface forms. However, there remains a central problem in designing fully fledged register analyses of texts like constitutional documents. Without a cogent definition or at least intuition of constitutional register(s), it's difficult to determine exactly which linguistic features are characteristic of the variation at hand. As such, a necessary step towards a program of constitutional register analysis will have to be a quantitative analysis of distributional patterns of linguistic features, which will be highlighted in Section 4.2.

The annotation of linguistic variables for this corpus consists of **lemma**, **parts-of-speech**, **clauses**, **compounds** and **lists**. Lemma and part-of-speech tags offer both the basic lemmatized form of respective tokens and their syntactical-morphological categorization. Both annotations were conducted automatically using the software TreeTagger 3.3.2 and corrected manually on the basis of Stuttgart-Tübingen-Tagset (Schiller et al. 1999). The **clause** layer is an annotation on the sentential level, marking both main and subordinate clauses of each sentence. The focus on compounds (tier **comp**) derives from the morphologically productive appearance of nominal determinative compounds which combine two freely occurring morphemes, where the head of the compound is modified by additional material (Lüdeling et al. 2023: 4). In the case of constitutions, these often denote stately institutions like governmental bodies or laws like *Amtsgericht* 'district court'. They predominantly rely on lexemes which refer to federal hierarchies of government e.g. *Landesgericht* 'Federal court' or *Reichstag* 'Reichstag'. As a subordinate hypothesis of this project, it is assumed that these kinds of compounds are at least in part characteristic of official or legal documents, contributing to a nominal style (Hennig 2020: 71). And lastly, the list layer notes the presence of listicle elements within any specific norms, organized by numeral (or alphabetical) elements. These often appear within legislative text sections, outlining different areas of jurisdiction, for example in Art. 7 Abs. 1 WRV.

In the next step, the specific discursive grounding of any potential variation across and within texts will be explored. To accommodate the combination of

linguistic material with discursive markers, we will have to look at the operationalization and annotation of situational-functional parameters on the normative level.

3.3.2. Situational-functional variables

The discursive contexts of text production are defined by a multitude of different factors and variables. Communicative situations are characterized by producer and receiver, the relationship or interaction between the two, e.g. social standing or rank, the communicative functions and goals, the medium of language production, its themes, etc. (Beier et al. 2023: 492). All take part in influencing contextual variation of language use. Formalization of some of these factors into suitable variables turned out to be difficult, since constitutions represent very specific and idiosyncratic text types. Close readings of normative theories as well as commentaries on constitutional law informed the choices undertaken in constructing the following categories.

After interacting with the relevant documents for the first time, it seemed appropriate to split the register variables into two types: structural annotations and more targeted situation-functional annotations. The structural annotations are derived from surface level markers of categorization within the text like chapter titles, as well as the underlying structural logic in the construction of the constitutional documents. As a result, the structural annotation layers are **section_1** and **section_2**, which represent the divisions of the documents by title and subtitles²³. The second-layer structure of basic elements and components of the normative structure are **article**, **paragraph** and **sentence**. The first two are again determined by relying on orthographic markers (ordinals, line breaks, etc.), whereas the sentential layer is not marked separately. These variables are useful for informing insights into the macro- and microstructural levels of the constitutional documents, allowing for a clear determination of boundaries and scope of functional and situational contexts. Since these structures, divisions and categorizations are basic features of jurisprudential literature and practice (Rüthers et al. 2021; Stein & Frank 2010), they serve as a fitting foundation for applying value tags to more abstract discursive considerations. Knowing the basic units structuring constitutional texts allows for the attribution of proper communicative and discursive features.

²³ Constitutions in this corpus contain either one or two macrostructural layers. If there is only one, the sections are annotated on **section_1**.

These second-order register variables circumscribe the discursive context of the documents and their text units. They are annotated on the layers of **direction (dir)**, **type**, **form**, **genre** and **topic**, the first three being tethered to the **paragraph** layer. In total, these variables aim to capture some qualities of the different dimensions of register phenomena. The directionality of the norms aims to elucidate notions of address, while the layers form and type outline the basic functional continuum contained within constitutional norms. Genre and topic serve as situational backgrounding on a textual level, dividing the documents into larger structures and assigning both a genre label as a marker of underlying text type and a topic label as a broader categorization of state goals. What is missing from this formalization of communicative context is the notion of medium or channel, since dissemination is always written and bound to a singular textual production.

With both the linguistic variables offering an insight into distributions of linguistic features and register variables staking out communicative and discursive spaces, we can approach a first investigation into their correlation and the emergence of patterns of conventionalized language use. Important to note is that these variables are immanent to the relevant text bodies, meaning that they represent the variation of exogenous features within the documents themselves. However, there are also features that carry across the entire constitutional documents and vary only on the intertextual level, which is why they will be annotated as metadata.

3.3.3. Metadata

The last set of situational variables is annotated as metadata appended to each document, thereby applying to all tokens within the sub-corpora. In essence, these variables can be understood as text-spanning variables as opposed to the text-immanent variables outlined above. The list of metadata variables contains: the official titles of the constitutions, state, designations of the states, dates of ratification, capitals, original signatories and editions (with sources). These layers all pertain to official and bibliographical information about the individual documents to ensure proper documentation of the entire project. The metadata, above all the assigning of title and state belonging, can also be interpreted as supplying additional information about situational context. As Egbert & Gracheva (2023) show, the primary speakers of American presidential speeches, for example, can bound the communicative space of text productions (2023: 131). Followingly, it makes sense to understand the issuer and ratifier

of the constitutional document, i.e. the underlying states, as the producers of the texts and their communicative goals. On this basis, I have decided to add two additional situational variables based on historical-political research: the official political system of the individual states (**system**), as well as their conditions of emergence, the latter being an experimental and explorative variable (**process**). These two variables ground the constitutional documents within their respective historical settings, aiming to factorize potential variations based on either political-ideological formations²⁴ or the administrative-economical contingencies of state emergence²⁵. Since the constructed corpus is both diachronic and concerned with political matters, these metadata annotations offer a necessary contextualization for any project of register analysis of constitutional or plainly legal documents, for that matter. However, they should be handled carefully, as historical reconstruction of situational context is extremely difficult (Lüdeling et al. 2022: 9-10). While systemic considerations are parts of the constitutions themselves and there exists ample historical material on German state development, the ultimate validity of these variables is debatable.

Before continuing with explicit annotation examples in the guidelines, there are some other considerations that had to be taken into account with regards to corpus construction and (meta-)data annotation. Deciding on the structuring principles governing the individual text documents was an important step in the design of the corpus and its subordinate parts. It would have been possible to conjoin the individual texts within a single annotation document, thereby leaving the metadata as the only distinguishing feature between tokens. On the one hand, such a totalizing view upon the data structure, basically eliminating distinct subordinate corpora (at least within the graphical representation of the search engine ANNIS), would have blurred the boundaries between individual documents. On the other hand, this would have potentially shifted the perception of the communicative and discursive context embedded within certain annotation layers. In such a total view of the data, the layers of **genre** and **topic** would more readily be interpreted as kinds of metadata of distinct units of text. Since both layers apply to large passages of text, the resulting annotation within one large corpus would have highlighted the more comparative nature of such a project, stressing commonalities and differences between increasingly smaller discursive units.

²⁴ Realized within this thesis as either *monarchical* or *republican* as outlined by the respective constitutions.

²⁵ Either in a wholesale project of nation building or a more anodyne process of state transformation (Kocka 2021).

While this approach certainly would have offered a useful perspective on intra-textual variation (H₂), the centrality of the inter-textual project remained more important.

3.4. Annotation guidelines

The following section details the different annotation layers with descriptions, processual information and examples. A documentation of the selected texts (i.e. sub-corpora) can be found in the Appendix (Section 9.1.).

Base layers:

Layer name: **word**

Description: Base textual layer, individual tokens of constitutional documents. Representation without modification or orthographic adjustment to retain original form.

Tools: TreeTagger 3.2.3

Process: Automatic tokenization, manual correction.

Segmentation: Base segmentation for the entire corpus (as the token layer).

Layer name: **norm**

Description: Layer for normalized representations of the textual tokens to establish compatibility between texts. Since German orthographical standards and conventions have been subject to multiple changes over the timespan covered by the corpus, tokens are adjusted to modern phonological and orthographical rules.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual correction followed by retokenization of adjusted version; secondary manual review.

Values:

Orthographical correction:

- | | | | | |
|-----|----|-------|---|--------|
| (1) | a. | müßen | → | müssen |
| | | must | | |
| | b. | Jahre | → | Jahr |
| | | year | | |

c. Rathe → Rat
assembly

Phonological correction:

(2) giebt → gibt
give

Segmentation: Base segmentation, based on the **word** (token) layer.

Layer name: **abr**

Description: Layer containing the lemmata of abbreviations within the original text.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual tagging. Multi-word abbreviations (e.g. *ff.* ‘and the following’) are not segmented and correspond to the original token on the **word** layer.

Examples:

(3) a. Bundesgesetzbl. → Bundesgesetzblatt
Federal Law Gazette
b. usw. → und so weiter
and so forth

Segmentation: Base segmentation, based on the **word** (token) layer.

Linguistic layers:

Layer name: **pos**

Description: Layer containing annotation for individual parts-of-speech corresponding to the tokens on the norm layer.

Tools: TreeTagger 3.2.3

Process: Initial automatic tagging process followed by normalization. Retagging of normalized output, followed by manual review and correction.

Values: Tagset provided by STTS (Stuttgart-Tübingen-Tagset)

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Layer name: **lemma**

Description: Linguistic annotation of lemmata (i.e. reference word forms without person, number, case, etc.) for the corresponding tokens on the **norm** layer.

Tools: TreeTagger 3.2.3

Process: Automatic lemmatization followed by manual review and correction.

Values: Lemmatization.

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Layer name: **clause**

Description: Span annotation marking the extent and type of individual clauses of sentences.

Tools: Microsoft Excel

Process: Manual annotation (since automatic sentence parsing proved inconsistent).

Values: main (for main clauses), sub (for subordinate clauses).

Segmentation: Based on the **norm** layer.

Layer name: **comp**

Motivation: Constitutional texts appear to be highly morphologically productive with regards to composition processes. There are a significant number of nouns that correspond to governmental bodies, institutions, laws, concepts and the like. They are of the determinative type (cf. Section 3.3.1.), combining a head with additional semantic material (Lüdeling et al. 2023: 4) . For the purposes of this study, the **comp** layer is divided into four values. The first and most important describes compounds based on federal instances of government, from the abstract state level (*Staat* ‘state’, *Volk* ‘people’), to the federal (*Bund* ‘federal (state)’, *Land* ‘state’) to the local level (*Gemeinde* ‘municipality’, *Bezirk* ‘district’), etc. The second is concerned with compounds of the same type, though not derived from federal instances. These can refer to more general applications of institutional frameworks. The other two values contain the respective base forms for both values (i.e. the heads of each compound). This separation is

informed by the hypothesized productivity of the noun(FED) + noun(HEAD) combination²⁶.

Description: Annotation of determinative compounds denoting governmental and institutional concepts.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation using filter function of the tabulation software; filtering for individual forms.

Values: y_f (compounds with non-head based on federal instances of government), n_f (base form of the non-head of y_f), y_b (compounds with non-head based on other nominal material), n_b (base form of of the non-head of y_b)

Examples for y_f:

- (4) Bundesrat, Reichstag, Landesgesetz, Volksabstimmung, Staatsangehörige, Reichseisenbahn
Bundesrat, Reichstag, federal state law, popular referendum, citizens, imperial rail

Exxamples for y_b:

- (5) Wahlperiode, Passwesen, Grenzschutz, Niederlassungserlaubnis, Wehrverfassung, Schifffahrtsabgabe
election period, passport system, border security, settlement permit, military constitution, shipping toll

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Layer name: **list**

Motivation: Annotation of lists (or listicles) within individual norms. These often take different forms, i.e. are either denoted by ordinals (1., 2., 3., etc.) or letters (a., b., c., etc.). There is no systematic denotation of listings observable, whether one or the other is picked seems to be random.

Description: Span annotation marking the presence of listicles within individual norms.

²⁶ This is in contrast to the second category, which doesn't explicitly have to be derived from the sphere of government (e.g. law, economics, etc.).

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual span annotation.

Values: y (yes)

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Structural layers:

As mentioned in the previous section, there are two macrostructural levels. The overarching categorization of different articles into themed groupings is designated by layers **section_1**, accounting for the broadest collections of norms like basic rights or state organization, while the second-order layer, **section_2**, represents subdivisions of the first group based on a topical logic. These sections describe either the inner workings of individual state institutions and bodies, or the topical area of basic rights. However, these categorical variables only denote the structural boundaries found within the text (through titles and headings). *Values* should be annotated with this in mind; the situational annotation of these structures will be elaborated later.

Layer name: **section_1**

Description: Span annotation of macrostructural text units such as chapters or sections.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on chapter headings.

Values: Iterative values derived by section headings, normalized by use of the term *Teil*, e.g. Teil 1, Teil 2, etc.

- (6) a. A. Grundlagen der Staatsgewalt.
A. Basic of state power.
(DDR 1949)
- b. Zweiter Hauptteil: Grundrechte und Grundpflichten der Deutschen
Second chapter: Basic rights and obligations of the German people
(WRV)

Segmentation: Based on **article** layer.

Layer name: **section_2**

Description: Span annotation of second-order macrostructural text units, specifically individual sections within chapters.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual Annotation based on section titles.

Values: Iterative values derived by section headings, normalized by use of the term *Abschnitt* 'section', e.g. Abschnitt 1, Abschnitt 2, etc.

- (7) a. Artikel VI.
Article VI.
(Abschnitt VI. Paulskirchenverfassung)
- b. Kapitel 3. Die Gewerkschaften und Ihre Rechte
Chapter 3. The unions and their rights.
(Abschnitt I. DDRV 1968)

Segmentation: Based on **article** layer.

The second group of macrostructural layers are tethered to the norm itself. The **article** (*Artikel*) spans the entire norm and is the most basic representation of its collated content. Articles represent the base level of normative hierarchy. They bundle functional and situational considerations. Within the categorization employed in this thesis, articles function as somewhat loose, thematically bound (supra)norms. They can exhibit multiple normative areas and programs.

This multitude is captured by the subsequent layer: **paragraph** (*Absatz*), which denotes the second-order structural layer of the norm. The paragraph is bounded by bracketed ordinals. Paragraphs embody more specific functions of the norm. They highlight certain components of the normative area or program, can represent individual norms themselves, or function as additional imperatives addressed to governing bodies. Some paragraphs stand as norms on their own, others only work in tandem with other paragraphs (or even articles themselves).

The functional specificity is shared by the last structural normative layer: the sentence layer **sent** (*Satz*) Sentences comprise the smallest unit of normative composition (and analysis). They are not specifically denoted within most common editions

of constitutional texts. Separation is achieved through denotation of syntactic markers, such as punctuation. Sentences function more broadly as an analytical category integral to the systematic understanding of normative structures within constitutional law²⁷. Sentences do not represent individual norms themselves, unless the norm itself is bound by a single sentence. They function only as specifications for other components of the norm. While not integrated into this thesis program, sentences cover an even more granular and complex functional space. In relation to the normative area and program, they are best understood as modifications upon the form (cf. **form** layer): as limits, inhibitions, redirections, enable acts, etc.

Layer name: **article**

Description: Span annotation covering the extent of individual articles.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation. Each annotation starts with the token sequence of *Artikel #* and ends with the final punctuation mark.

Values: Iterative values based on list and number of articles; use of conventionalized abbreviation *Art.*, e.g. Art. 1, Art. 2, Art. 3, etc.

- (8) Artikel 13. Die Wohnung ist unverletzlich
Article 13. The place of residence is inviolable.
(Art. 13 GG)

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Layer name: **paragraph**

Description: Span annotation covering the extent of individual paragraphs within articles.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation. Each annotation starts with the token sequence (*#*) signaling the start of a paragraph and ends with the final punctuation mark before the next article or paragraph.

²⁷ The category is found within commentaries used by practitioners of the discipline, such as (Sachs et al. 2021).

Values: Iterative values based on paragraph number; use of the conventionalized abbreviation *Abs.*, e.g. *Abs. 1*, *Abs. 2*, *Abs. 3*, etc.

- (9) Art. 123 Abs. 2 Versammlungen unter freiem Himmel können durch Reichsgesetz anmeldepflichtig gemacht und bei unmittelbarer Gefahr für die öffentlich Sicherheit verboten werden.

Art. 123 Abs. 2 Open-air gatherings can be made notifiable through imperial law and be prohibited in case of immediate threat to public safety.

(Art. 123 Abs. 2 WRV)

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Layer name: **sent**

Description: Span annotation covering the extent of individual sentences within paragraphs.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation. Each annotation starts with the token after either the paragraph designation (#) or the token following the end of the previous sentence marked by a punctuation mark.

Values: Iterative values based on sentence number; use of the term *Satz*, e.g. *Satz 1*, *Satz 2*, *Satz 3*, etc.

- (10) Die Verhandlungen der Volkskammer und ihrer Ausschüsse sind öffentlich.

The proceedings of the People's Parliament and its committees are public.

(Art. 62 Abs. 1 S.1 DDRV 1949)

Segmentation: Based on **norm** layer.

Functional layers:

The functional layers apply to the basic textual unit of the constitutional archetype: the norm. For the purposes of this project, they are anchored on the level of the **paragraph** layer. This choice was informed by the ideas of normative areas and programs (Müller 1966: 184-186) which needed to be kept as discreet as possible, something

counteracted by the holistic approach of “articles as individual norms” (Müller 2007: 188-191). Still, even within the context of paragraphs, differentiations of normative content can be made out²⁸, which is why the sentential layer is also annotated.

Layer name: **dir**

Motivation: Constitution as text productions differ from other types of text in significant ways. Whereas belletristic or even official documents often have clear markers for the encompassed communicative spaces (i.e. author-reader relationship, inter-character-relations), constitutions diverge by producer and receiver being identical. It is the state and its various institutions and representatives that addresses itself on the axes of temporal displacement²⁹. As the foundational documents of states in toto, the readership still contains its legal subjects, most explicit in the basic laws conferred to inhabitants and citizens of a country. Its major orientation, however, rests on the state, its various interlocutors and interpreters (politicians, lawmakers, the courts, prosecutors, defense attorneys, local administrations, etc.). As such, the state is always producer and (in almost all instances) explicit receiver simultaneously. Nevertheless, the communicative directionality can still be modelled. One of the basic features of the law is to arbitrate instances of conflict between its legal subjects, meaning between private citizens themselves, between citizens and the state, as well as the state and itself. Constitutional law as part of public law outlines a state’s most basic functions, its limits and prescriptions for the legal order. Areas of conflict relating to private citizens are touched upon by necessity. The communicative dimension, more regularly embodied by speaker-addressee relationships or channels of communication, is modelled using the directionality of constitutional norms as basis. A third category can be proposed, representing norms that mediate not only between states and citizens, but between citizens themselves. Those types of constitutional norms represent the special category of *Drittwirkung von Grundrechten* ‘third-party effect of the fundamental rights’ (Manssen 2024: 48). They represent an addendum to the public-private dichotomy, which is however left out of this project due to being limited to the Grundgesetz.

Determining the “correct” value of the direction layer during annotation is based on a variety of factors. A simple heuristic can be the comparison with normative type. Basic rights aimed at citizens and other non-state actors very often mediate

²⁸ Particularly within longer paragraphs.

²⁹ Since laws generally permeate across time and are continually adjusted, adjudicated and reinterpreted.

potential conflicts between the state and the public sphere. Since norms are largely built out of multiple paragraphs containing different specific functions, a blanket application of the values *öffentlich* ‘public’ or *staat* ‘state’ based entirely on normative type would distort the annotation. For example, there are multiple basic rights whose concrete actualization as law is left up to the state’s prerogative, initialized by the phrase *Das Nähere regelt ein Gesetz* ‘Further details are to be regulated by law’. These norms, while embedded in public-directed basic rights, should be understood as the state establishing its own legislative boundaries, and therefore annotated with *staat*. Another useful shorthand is the analysis of scope and plurality of subjects within norms. Usually, norms containing generalized quantifiers refer to sets of individuals (i.e. non-state actors). Similarly, when the most salient subject of a norm denotes either concrete individuals or abstracted sets thereof, as opposed to governmental bodies (eg. *Deutsche* ‘Germans’ vs. *Bundestag* ‘parliament’), it usually refers to public-directed norms under our definition. Of course, there are norms where a simple recourse to linguistic material fails. Norms lacking personalized subjects³⁰ are harder to categorize, in which case the reference to standard commentaries or other constitutions can be useful.

Description: Span annotation marking the direction of normative content between the public and private sphere.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on interpretation of normative content

Values: staat, öffentlich

Example for public-directed norms corresponding to basic rights:

(11) Art. 8 Abs. 1 Alle Deutschen haben das Recht, sich ohne Anmeldung oder Erlaubnis friedlich und ohne Waffen zu versammeln.

Art. 8 Abs. 1 All Germans have the right to peacefully gather without arms.

(Art. 8 Abs. 1 GG)

(12) Art. 103 Abs. 3 Niemand darf wegen der selben Tat aufgrund der allgemeinen Strafgesetze mehrmals bestraft werden.

³⁰ Such as Art. 6, Abs. 1 GG: *Ehe und Familie stehen unter dem besonderen Schutze der staatlichen Ordnung*. ‘Marriage and the family are protected by the State’

Art. 103 Abs. 3 No person may be punished for the same act more than once under the general criminal laws.

(Art. 103 Abs. 3 GG)

A as *öffentlich* tagged norm that is part of the organizational sections of the constitution. It describes principles of democratic legitimation (electability for office of President) and applies to individuals as non-state actors:

(13) Art. 41 Abs. 2 Wählbar ist jeder Deutsche, der das fünfunddreißigste Lebensjahr vollendet hat.

Art. 41 Abs. 2 Every German who has completed the 35th year of age is electable.

(Art. 41 Abs. 2 WRV)

Example of a state-directed norm:

(14) Art. 50 Abs. 1 Höchstes Organ der Republik ist die Volkskammer.

Art. 50 Abs. 1 The highest organ of the republic is the people's chamber.

(Art. 50 Abs. 1 DDRV 1949)

A norm annotated as "staat" within the basic rights paradigm:

(15) Art. 138 Abs. 6 Die für das Heer- und Seewesen erforderlichen Modifikationen dieser Bestimmungen werden besonderen Gesetzen vorbehalten.

Art. 138 Abs. 6 The necessary modifications of the provision of military and naval matters are reserved to special laws.

(§138 Abs. 6 Paulskirchenverfassung)

There are contentious cases, though. The following, for example, is annotated as *öffentlich* despite usually being handled otherwise. This comes as a result of the specific provision being integrated into the larger norm (as one sentence of four). The rest of the paragraph is judged as exerting stronger force on its directional qualities, resulting in its annotation

(16) Art. 104 Abs. 2 [...] Das Nähere ist gesetzlich zu regeln.

Art. 104 Abs. 2 [...] Further details are to be regulated by law.

(Art. 104 Abs. 2 S. 4 GG)

The following example also highlights the difficulty in applying discreet annotations. While the first is annotated as *öffentlich*, the second is annotated as *staat*. The decision was made on basis of the semantic content of the respective nominals.

Auswanderungsfreiheit is taken to mean citizens' right to emigration while *Auswanderungsangelegenheiten* refers to the state's preoccupation with matters of emigration.

(17) Art. 136 Abs. 1 Die Auswanderungsfreiheit ist von Staatswegen nicht beschränkt; Abzugsgelder dürfen nicht erhoben werden.

Art. 136 Abs. 1 The right to emigration is not limited by the state; escape fees shall not be levied.

Abs. 2 Die Auswanderungsangelegenheit steht unter dem Schutze und der Fürsorge des Reiches.

Abs. 2 The matter of emigration is in the purview of the state and protected by it.

(Art. 136 Abs. 1, 2 Paulskirchenverfassung)

Segmentation: Based on **paragraph** layer.

Layer name: **type**

The second exogenous variable describes the basic function of norms within the constitutions. As outlined above, there are two basic parts to most modern constitutions: basic (civil) rights and organizational norms. The first are occupied with outlining the essential basic rights of legal subjects, limits upon the state's power to act in conflict with those rights, and certain prescriptions and obligations the state has a responsibility to fulfill. On the other hand, organizational norms describe the basic bodies, institutions and features of the state. They establish the processes by which these institutions come about, are decided upon or dissolved. Organizational norms can themselves be subdivided into two categories: institutional norms, which outline the procedural aspects of institutional legitimization, and functional norms, which describe the functional purview of the state (Stein and Frank 2010: 4-5). In a first annotation of the Federal Republic of Germany's constitution, this distinction was also marked. Ultimately, a simpler version of the annotation was decided upon, choosing to retain the more fundamental division of basic rights and organizational norms, annotated as *grundrecht* 'basic right' and *organisation* 'organization'.

Deciding on the value assignment during annotation is often achieved by broad categorization of text sections. Basic rights almost exclusively appear within their respective sections and organizational norms within theirs. Additionally, the heuristic for the direction variable of determining sets of individuals vs. state bodies can help

as well. These simplifications cannot be applied universally, though. There are norms granting specific rights to individual representatives and members of the state, for example. These should not be annotated as basic rights. The definition of basic rights applies only to non-state actors. In contrast to the previous category, special provisions within individual norms like *Gesetzesvorbehalte* ‘reservation of statutory powers’ (Manssen 2024: 65). are not annotated with *organisation* since the provision unfolds its meaning in conjunction with the normative program of the entire norm. Specifications of basic rights are therefore part of the norm and should be annotated as such.

Description: Span annotation marking the functional type of the described norm.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on interpretation of normative content.

Values: grundrecht, organisation

Examples of basic rights:

- (18) Art. 153 Abs. 1 Das Eigentum wird von der Verfassung gewährleistet.
Art. 153 Abs. 1 Private property is guaranteed by the constitution.
(Art. 153 Abs. 1 WRV)
- (19) Art. 14 Abs. 3 Privatwirtschaftlichen Vereinigungen zur Begründung wirtschaftlicher Macht sind nicht gestattet.
Art. 14 Abs. 3 Commercial associations aimed at gaining economic power are prohibited.
(Art. 14 Abs. 3 DDRV 1968)
- (20) Art. 4 Abs. 3 Niemand darf gegen sein Gewissen zum Kriegsdienst mit der Waffe gezwungen werden.
Art. 4 Abs. 3 No one can be forced to military service against their consciousness.
(Art. 4 Abs. 3 GG)

Examples of state organizational norms:

- (21) Art. 29 Abs. 1 Die Mitglieder des Reichstages sind Vertreter des gesamten Volkes und an Aufträge und Instruktionen nicht gebunden.
Art. 29 Abs. 1 The members of the Reichstag are the representatives of the people and not bound by orders nor instructions.
(Art. 29 DRV)

(22) Art. 88 Abs. 3 Staatsverträge, die sich auf Gegenstände der Gesetzgebung beziehen, sind wie Gesetze zu verkünden.

Art. 88 Abs. 3 State contracts that pertain to objects of legislation are to be proclaimed like laws.

(Art. 88 Abs. 3 DDRV 1949)

Segmentation: Based on **paragraph** layer.

Layer name: **form**

The content of the layer **form** relates most strongly to the basic communicative function displayed by constitutional norms. The **type** variable describes base legal functions within a broader legal system, i.e. which normative spaces within the state's legal system norms inhibit. What the **type** variable lack is an explanation of the base mechanism by which the superseding goals are achieved. Some norms enable and empower the state to create new laws, institutions, bodies, positions, etc., others simply establish legal realities by fiat³¹, others again limit the state's power to act in breach of certain rights, etc. How are these different functional paradigms enshrined and made to be applicable legal precedent? Section 2.3.2. presents the theoretical foundation for this endeavor. Abstracting away from the concrete legal content of the norms, their primary communicative purpose as a subset of social norms is highlighted. As such, norms are assigned two main communicative functions: establishing discursive facts by way of constitutive norms and inducing behaviors through so-called prescriptive norms. Prescriptive norms are those that compel the state to act in certain fashions, force the state to implement certain orders, or severely limit its ability to act by way of sanctions. Constitutive norms, on the other hand, are those norms which create the conditions for further explications of statecraft itself. They describe legal realities, confer basic rights to legal subjects, and operationalize instances of the state. The values are *konstitutiv* 'constitutive' and *preskriptiv* 'prescriptive'. Since normative form is a rather abstract and ambiguous category, annotation is not easy. The most systematic annotation can be achieved by observation of different features due to the intimate relation between legal function of a norm and its surface level representation.

Value assignment for the form variable is predicated on a mix of legal categorization and analysis of linguistic material. For example, norms which place boundaries and limits upon the state's powers should be taken as prescriptive. This type of

³¹ Examples are the establishment of state boundaries and borders, official colors, etc.

norm is often denoted by deontic obligational modals, such as *muss* ‘must’ or *darf* ‘may’ with negation. Other prescriptive norms take the form of nominalized obligation, which is signaled through verbal phrases like *ist die Aufgabe* ‘is the task of’ or *hat die Pflicht* ‘has the obligation’. Negation in general often occurs as constriction on capabilities and serves as an indicator of prescription. Constitutive norms, on the other hand, are often established by use of declarative phrases employing finite verbs or finite auxiliaries (chiefly the lemma *werden* ‘will’) in combination with other material. However, the annotation should not exclusively rely on verbal classes. For example, we can observe an inverted mapping of meanings in case of split infinitives. Those norms initialized by the auxiliary *haben das Recht* ‘to have the right’ are often followed by split infinitives outlining capacities or permissions to act in certain ways, while those norms headed by the auxiliary of *sein* ‘to be’ are more likely to be followed by split infinitives signaling obligational provisions (e.g. *ist...zu entsenden* ‘is to be dispatched’ Art. 15 Abs. 2 WRV). Other contributions to annotation decisions are supplied by additional salient material, e.g. predicate adjectives like *verboten* ‘prohibited’ or *erforderlich* ‘necessary’.

Description: Span annotation marking the concrete normative form of the described paragraph.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on normative interpretation.

Values: konstitutiv, preskriptiv

Base examples of constitutive norms, employing finite verbs or deontic modals of possibility:

- (23) Art. 61 Abs. 1 Der Bundestag oder Bundesrat können den Bundespräsidenten wegen vorsätzlicher Verletzung des Grundgesetzes oder eines anderen Bundesgesetzes vor dem Bundesverfassungsgericht anklagen. [...] Art. 61 Abs. 1 The Bundestag or Bundesrat can bring charges against the Federal President in front of the Constitutional Court on the basis of pre-mediated violation of the Basic Law or other federal Law.
(Art. 61 Abs. 1 S. 1 GG)
- (24) Art. 49 Abs. 1 Der Reichspräsident übt für das Reich das Begnadigungsrecht aus.

Art. 49 Abs. 1 The President of the Reich exercises the right to pardon for the Reich.

(Art. 49 Abs. 1 WRV)

Examples of prescriptive norms containing deontic modals of obligation (incl. negation), specific verbal phrases or predicate adjectives.

- (25) Art. 26 Abs. 1 Ohne die Zustimmung des Reichstages darf die Vertagung desselben die Frist von 30 Tagen nicht übersteigen und während der selben Session nicht wiederholt werden.

Art. 26 Abs. 1 Without its consent, the adjournment of the Reichstag can't exceed the 30-day term nor be resumed within the same session.

(Art. 26 Abs. 1 DRV)

- (26) Art. 66 Abs. 8 Die Feststellung der Verfassungswidrigkeit von Regierungs- und Verwaltungsmaßnahmen ist Aufgabe der Volkskammer in Durchführung der ihr übertragenen Verwaltungskontrolle.

Art. 66 Abs. 8 The observation of unconstitutionality of governmental and administrative provision is responsibility of the people's chamber in execution of its conferred administrative control.

(Art. 66 Abs. 8 DDRV 1949)

- (27) Art. 98 Abs. 1 Zu einem Beschluß eines jeden Hauses des Reichstages ist die Teilnahme von wenigstens der Hälfte der gesetzlichen Anzahl seiner Mitglieder und die einfache Stimmenmehrheit erforderlich.

Art. 98 Abs. 1 The attendance of at least half of its legally required members is necessary for any of the chambers of the Reichstag to pass any decision. A simple majority of votes is required.

(§98 Abs. 1 Paulskirchenverfassung)

- (28) Art. 60 Abs. 1 Alle staatlichen und wirtschaftlichen Organe sind dazu verpflichtet, die Abgeordneten bei der Wahrung ihrer Aufgaben zu unterstützen.

Art. 60 Abs. 1. All public and commercial bodies are required to support the representatives in the conduct of their duties.

(Art. 60 Abs. 1 DDRV 1969)

Segmentation: Based on **paragraph** layer.

Situational layers:

The following set of variables can be ascribed to the “situational” continuum of the register paradigm. As such, they are contextual addenda to the structural annotation of the sectional division of constitutional texts. They bundle huge volumes of tokens and always represent collections of multiple norms. These variables are based on the premediated categorization of the constitutional texts through their titles and chapter headings. These illuminate the functional-situational scope of the norm collections.

Layer name: genre

Motivation: This layer is modelled on the largest sectional layer, **section_1**. The basic division of constitutions into different paradigms, like prefaces or civil (basic laws and rights) and organizational matters. In the Grundgesetz of the Federal Republic of Germany, for example, the first 19 articles are collectively known as the basic rights (*Grundrechte*), while the remaining 127 articles outline the characteristics of the state. This, however, does not cleanly map onto the categorization of individual norms, as organizational considerations can be found within the basic rights and vice versa. Therefore, it makes sense to interpret these large divisions as situational-functional paradigms in their own right. Annotation follows the structural annotation (**section_1**) and is determined by general content of the norms therein, if not outright stated by chapter and section headings.

Description: Span annotation based on macrostructural subsections (**section_1**), dividing the textual units into different “text types” or “genres”.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on chapter and section headings, content of sections.

Values: Präambel (preface), Grundrechte (basic rights), Staatsorganisation (state organization), Schlussbestimmung (closing provisions), Kundgebung (announcements)

- (29) Abschnitt III. Aufbau und System der staatlichen Leitung
Section III. Structure and system of state administration.
(Abschnitt III. DDRV 1968)
- (30) Abschnitt VI. Die Grundrechte des deutschen Volks.
Section VI. The basic rights of the German People.
(Abschnitt VI. Paulskirchenverfassung)

- (31) Präambel. Im Bewusstsein seiner Verantwortung vor Gott und den Menschen, [...]
 Preface. In the knowledge of its responsibility to god and humanity, [...]
 (Prämbel GG)
- (32) Übergangs- und Schlussbestimmungen. Art. 166 [...]
 Interim and closing provisions.
 (Übergang- und Schlussbestimmungen WRV)

Segmentation: Based on the **section_1** layer.

Layer name: **topic**

Motivation: The second situational layer is based on the structural layer **section_2**, outlining the individual subsections within constitutions. These second-order sections are generally concerned with specific instances and branches of the state, as well as their basic functions and capabilities. For example, every constitution contains a section on the basic construction of their respective parliaments, heads of states, lawmaking capabilities, etc. The only major outlier is the constitution of 1871, which goes further and subdivides these into even more technocratic aspects of state capabilities³². As each state also employs different naming conventions for itself and its various bodies, the values for the **topic** variable had to be normalized to achieve inter-operability between individual sub-corpora. Since all of the modern states employ some kind of functional distribution of state capabilities, the tokens were categorized according to the branch of government that each of the sections describes. Parliamentary sections belong to the *Legislative* ‘legislative’, whereas the central governmental body will be annotated with the tag *Exekutive* ‘executive’, the sections on courts with *Judikative* ‘judiciary’, and so forth. For sections on federal hierarchies and matters of lower-order administration, the label *Verwaltung* ‘administration’ was added. Another addition is the *Systematik* ‘systematics’ value, which is used for provisions that are concerned with transit terms (i.e. *Schluss- und Übergangsbestimmungen*). The second set of values is based on topics covered by the basic rights. There is no unified categorization of basic rights across constitutions, e.g. the 1919 constitution marks the thematical categorization of the basic rights, whereas the 1949 constitution of the FRG lacks such surface-level markers. Since basic rights often inhibit the same normative areas and programs

³² Such as sovereignty over rail or naval matters (Abschnitt VII., Abschnitt IX., DRV)

across constitutions, a topical annotation can be extrapolated. Based on the broad collection of these norms, the values for this set are: *Basis* ‘basic’, *Familie* ‘family’, *Religion* ‘religion’, *Bildung* ‘education’ and *Wirtschaft* ‘economy’. The tag *Basis* is a unique value that isn’t really marked in the constitutions. It denotes those rights granted to every person regardless of their belonging to other units of social organization (e.g. freedom of speech, etc.).

Description: Span annotations assigning topical content to superstructural textual units based on **section_2** (or **section_1** in case there is only one structural layer).

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation based on chapter and section headings; deriving topical assignment by reference to governmental branches occupied by governmental bodies

Values:

For basic rights: Basis, Familie, Religion, Wirtschaft, Bildung;

For state organization: Exekutive, Legislative, Judikative, Verwaltung, Haushalt, Staatsgrundladen, Systematik

- (33) Vierter Abschnitt: Bildung und Schule.
Fourth Section: Education and the School system.
(Zweiter Hauptteil WRV)
- (34) Abschnitt IV. Der Reichstag
Section IV. The Reichstag.
(Abschnitt IV Paulskirchenverfassung)
- (35) Art. 4 Abs. 2 Die ungestörte Religionsausübung wird gewährleistet.
Art. 4 Abs. 2 Free exercise of religion is guaranteed.
(Art. 4, Abs. 2 GG)

Segmentation: Based on the token layer, anchored to **section_2**.

Meta layers:

There are various layers of meta-data that are additionally annotated and apply wholly to the respective sub-corpora. For archival and documentary purposes, these are: the name of the constitutions, the official names of the states in question, the dates of ratification, its original signatories, the place of ratification (i.e. the state capitals) and

the editions used. However, I have chosen to include two additional meta-annotation layers to expand the contextual frame of the individual corpora: systems of government and processes of state creation. Both aim to illuminate the historical-situational context that is described and prescribed within the constitutional framework.

Layer name: **system**

Motivation: The first variable offers a description of the system of government found in each historical instance. This annotation provides insight into the relation between forms of government and its legal foundation. While all states are situated within the modern constitutional paradigm of the post-Napoleonic order in Europe, the structural make-up of the states still differs to some degree. Both the earliest constitutions in the corpus describe systems of constitutional monarchy anchored around the imperial heads of state. The monarchical system in Germany is abolished with the revolution of 1919, ushering in a parliamentary federal republic. Following the defeat and fall of the Nazi regime, two states are founded within the former state boundaries of the Third Reich; both are federal parliamentary republics. However, the GDR creates a new constitution in 1968 following the dissolution of its federal hierarchy, enshrining the “real-socialist” unitary state in its constitutions.

Description: Meta-annotation of the political system of organization.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation derived from close reading and research of relevant literature.

Values: Konstitutionelle Monarchie, Föderale Republik, Sozialistischer Einheitsstaat (cf. Section 2.4.2.)

Segmentation: Meta-annotation on the entire sub-corpus.

Layer name: **process**

Motivation: The last contextual annotation layer is the experimental category **process**, aiming to capture qualities of state formation processes in each historical instance, i.e. conditions and circumstances of the rise of each observed state. Because of the multitude of contingent factors determining state emergence, the category is reduced to only two values: state *building* and state *transition*. The first describes the wholesale

creation of a new state paradigm, abolishing the previous legal and constitutional order either entirely or in large part. The states in question are subject to significant upheavals of their political economies, whereas retention of much of the previous order signals state transition. As this annotation is based on the historical-political literature, detailed information on the development of the German states can be found in Section 2.4.2.

Description: Meta annotation of the historical conditions and processes of state formation surrounding the relevant political instances.

Tools: Excel

Process: Manual annotation derived from close reading and research of relevant literature.

Values: Building, Transition

Segmentation: Meta-annotation on the entire sub-corpus.

4. Case studies and statistical analysis

The following chapter encompasses two goals: a) demonstrating the technical capabilities of the corpus and showing off potential avenues for research, as well as; b) presenting an initial foray into the study of constitutional register. Within the first half, the structural make-up of the texts will be broken down, looking at all three layers of **article**, **paragraph** and **sentence**. Additionally, various case studies will be presented in order to highlight possible research programs, while tying the technical demonstration to analyses of situation-functional variation. This will be followed up on in the second half of the chapter, in which the corpus is viewed under the lens of the dimensional approach (Biber 2009). Potential featural distributions of constitutional texts and the therein contained subunits (e.g. basic rights or state organizational matters) will be staked out.

The statistical analysis and visualization of the data was conducted using Microsoft's Excel to import and aggregate .csv-data from the corpus-viewing search engine ANNIS, followed up by import and modification in the statistical software R³³ (R Core Team 2015), including the packages dplyr (Wickham et al. 2014), reshape2 (Wickham 2010), ggplot2 (Wickham et al. 2007), ggpubr (Kassambara 2016) and RColorbrewer (Neuwirth 2002).

4.1. Quantitative results: analysis of exogenous features

4.1.1. Structural features

Legal documents, in particular legislative texts³⁴, are highly structured textual productions. The same applies to constitutional documents, which are structured in multiple different ways: into broad types of texts (prefaces/preambles, basic rights, organizational matters), smaller chapters or sections (*Abschnitte*, *Teile*) and the basic units of legal meaning making in the form of the norm. With regards to the analysis of registers, the preexisting structures of constitutions are helpful in dividing the texts into reasonable subunits, which serve as the basis for the annotations of the corpus data. Analyzing structural features then offers a first insight into constitutional text productions and their specific hallmarks.

³³ Via R Studio Version 4.1.1 (RStudio Team 2016)

³⁴ Or more generally official administrative documents (Biber 1988: 128).

While all constitutions within the konkorp-corpus contain prefaces (*Präambel*) and some contain commencements (of the constitutions taking effect), the focus in this chapter rests on the concrete normative structural components of constitutional texts, i.e. the article and its subunits. Fig. 2, for example, depicts the average article length in tokens per constitution.

Fig. 2: Boxplot diagram showing the average lengths of articles (in tokens) across the constitutional documents.³⁵

Overall, the average length of an article across all documents is about 68.8 tokens (including punctuation). There is some degree of variation with the constitution of 1849 representing the lower boundary at 48.8 tokens and the Constitution of the German Empire (1871) setting the upper boundary at 89.7 tokens. While this degree of variation is significant, it can be explained by the differing amounts of individual paragraphs and sentences that make up the articles, respectively. Despite the outliers³⁶, the length of articles, paragraphs and sentences stays relatively consistent

³⁵ Titles in the illustrations are referred to by year and an abbreviation (in German).

³⁶ In most cases, the outliers can be explained by extremely long articles (both in raw token size, as well as paragraph/sentence volume, e.g. Art. 50 DRV with 276 tokens or Art. 53 DRV with five paragraphs),

across the different constitutions. Table 2 offers a complete breakdown of both token sizes, as well as averages for articles, paragraphs and sentences.

<i>Title</i>	<i>Tok_Art</i>	<i>Tok_Par</i>	<i>Tok_Sent</i>	<i># Art.</i>	<i># Par.</i>	<i># Sent.</i>	<i>Avg_Art.</i>	<i>Avg_Par.</i>	<i>Avg_Sent.</i>
<i>PKV</i>	9608	9016	8070	197	315	408	48,77	28,62	19,78
<i>DRV</i>	7449	7279	6810	83	157	211	89,75	46,36	32,27
<i>WRV</i>	11429	11070	10018	181	350	526	63,14	31,63	19,05
<i>GG</i>	12989	12698	11674	146	340	519	88,97	37,35	22,49
<i>DDRV49</i>	9148	8860	7891	144	323	439	63,53	27,43	17,97
<i>DDRV68</i>	8504	8288	7532	108	250	396	78,74	33,15	19,02
	59127	57211	51995	859	1735	2499	68,83	32,97	20,81

Table 2: Breakdown of total token numbers and averages for each constitutional text.

As we can see, the stark discrepancy in average article length is accompanied by more similar average lengths for both paragraphs and sentences. The constitution of 1871 is again somewhat of an outlier, with both paragraphs and sentences being about 12-14 tokens longer than the average (Table 2). The discrepancy itself can be explained by the fact that despite its short length, the individual articles, paragraphs and sentences each contain more material. In large part, this can be seen in articles in the sections about administrative matters like customs or warfare (VI., IX. DRV), which are characteristic of the text in the sense that they have no clear sectional counterparts in the other constitutional documents. It could be reasonable to assume that this variation can be explained by situational factors such as normative function or genre. Table 3 illustrates the average lengths of articles on basis of text type, showing averages for both basic rights and state organizational sections (**genre** in annotation). There is almost no difference in length between norms from one type or the other, the average lengths remaining close to the total average lengths across the entire corpus. This seems to indicate that, at least structurally speaking³⁷, there is close to no difference between the two individual text productions.

³⁷ This referring to the general normative layer.

<i>Genre</i>	<i>Tok_Total</i>	<i>Tok_Art.</i>	<i># Art.</i>	<i>Tok_Par.</i>	<i># Par.</i>	<i>Tok_Sent.</i>	<i># Sent.</i>
<i>State Organization</i>	38872	38557	564	37302	1098	33998	1580
<i>Basic Rights</i>	14069	13905	208	13428	460	12049	666
		<i>Avg Art. 1</i>	<i>Avg Art. 2</i>	<i>Avg Par. 1</i>	<i>Avg Par. 2</i>	<i>Avg Sent. 1</i>	<i>Avg Sent. 2</i>
<i>State Organization</i>		68,92	68,36	35,40	33,97	24,60	21,52
<i>Basic Rights</i>		67,64	66,85	30,58	29,19	21,12	18,09

Table 3: Breakdown of token volume and average article and paragraph length based on text type (state organization, basic rights). Averages calculated relative to both total token size and categorical token size (total tokens minus additional material like ordinals and brackets).

Another possible explanation for differences in article and paragraph lengths is their size not based on the number of tokens, but rather on the number of sentences per paragraph. Since norms can be represented by single sentences, analyzing the length of articles and paragraphs relative to the average number of sentences might better explain the difference. The following table (Table 4) breaks down the number of sentences, paragraphs and articles in each document with their average sentential lengths. The bottom half then shows the average length of individual paragraphs based on the number of sentences they bundle up.

	<i>#_Par.</i>	<i>#_Sent.</i>	<i>#_Art.</i>	<i>Avg_Par.</i>	<i>Avg_Art.</i>			
<i>PKV</i>	315	408	197	1,30	1,60			
<i>DRV</i>	157	211	83	1,34	1,89			
<i>WRV</i>	350	526	181	1,50	1,93			
<i>GG</i>	340	519	146	1,53	2,33			
<i>DDRV49</i>	323	439	144	1,36	2,24			
<i>DDRV68</i>	250	397	108	1,59	2,31			
<i>Avg Sent. per Par. #</i>	<i>Length_P1</i>	<i>Length_P2</i>	<i>lenthg_ab3</i>	<i>Length_P4</i>	<i>Length_P5</i>	<i>Length_P6</i>	<i>Length_P7</i>	<i>Length_P8</i>
<i>PKV</i>	1,40	1,16	1,12	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	
<i>DRV</i>	1,37	1,34	1,39	1,27	1,00	1,00		
<i>WRV</i>	1,61	1,34	1,49	1,48	1,36	1,17	1,00	1,00
<i>GG</i>	1,53	1,53	1,52	1,63	1,36	1,50	1,00	
<i>DDRV49</i>	1,47	1,23	1,31	1,50	1,08	1,50	1,00	1,00
<i>DDRV68</i>	1,66	1,55	1,60	1,50	1,20	1,33	1,00	1,00

Table 4: Total number of individual articles, paragraphs, sentences and average number of sentences per article and paragraph (above) and average number of sentences per individual paragraph number (below). Breakdown of sentences per paragraph number in the Appendix (9.3).

What we can see is that the average article is between 1.6-2.3 sentences and the average paragraph between 1.3-1.6 sentences long, with the constitution of 1849 again representing the lower boundary in both instances. This then explains the relative shortness of norms within the Paulskirchenverfassung. There is a proportionally higher number of single-sentence norms, including both in the form of articles and paragraphs. This applies to the constitution of 1871 as well, the extreme averages in Table 2 being a result of relative sentence length in tokens (32.3). Otherwise, paragraphs are on average 1.44 sentences long, while articles hover around 2.05 sentences.

Differences in the structural make-up of the documents can also be explored on the basis of linguistic features. E.g., it could be possible that earlier paragraphs of individual articles show a tendency towards sentence aggregation and coordination, as a result of a more nominally oriented declarative style (Hennig 2020: 160-164). The following figure (Fig. 3) illustrates the relative frequencies of subordinate clauses per numbered paragraph. Against expectations, the relative frequency of subordinate clauses remains stable over paragraph numbers (around thirty percent of all clauses), only tapering off beginning with paragraphs #5 and falling off with paragraphs #7. This seems to indicate that the writing style remains mostly consistent even across deeper layers of normative structures.

Fig. 3: Boxplot charting the relative frequency of subordinate clauses across paragraph numbers.

The next diagram (Fig. 4) illustrates the relative occurrence of finite verb forms and subordinate clauses across sentence number. While the relative occurrence of subordinate clauses again coalesces at around 30% for the most common sentence types (sentences one to three), finite verbs forms seem to occur mostly between 5%-9%. There are some instances of finite verb forms in the outliers of sentences four, five and six which contain instances of no subordinate clauses. Due to the relatively small sample size and infrequency of high sentence numbers³⁸, this doesn't seem to indicate any broader trends. However, the low frequency of finite verb forms within norms containing subordinate clauses seems to point away from a distinctly declarative style of writing.

Fig. 4: Relative frequency of determinative subordinate clauses and finite verbs by sentence number and title.

This short insight into structural features of constitutions illustrates one upside to working with the konkorp-corpus. In the following section, I will present small case studies that focus on the linguistic make-up of the corpus while touching on the impact of the situational-functional parameters structuring constitutional documents.

³⁸ Sentences ten and upward come from a single dataset, the constitution of 1849.

4.1.2. Situational-functional variation

While the previous analysis provided some ideas about how constitutional documents are structured, it didn't reveal much information about how the linguistic features are distributed across the corpus. The following section aims to explore some notable key features seemingly inherent to the constitutional form. These case studies and their concomitant research programs were derived through the familiarization with the documents and annotation of the corpus. Certain patterns or discrepancies appeared regularly enough to justify closer observation and analysis.

In the first instance, I decided to investigate the distribution of adjectives (both attributive and predicative) within the corpus. While constitutional documents don't usually display extremely descriptive features, adjective modification of nominal phrases is still common, again pointing to a nominal style within the corpus (Hennig 2020: 159-160). The following diagram (Fig. 5) shows the raw number of adjectives per individual sub-corpus. As we can see, the volume of adjectives remains constant until the constitutions of 1949, where a significant increase of adjectives can be observed. This trend is reflected when looking at the attributive adjective (ADJA) distributions relative to total token size, showing an uptick in 1949 (FRG: 6.3%) and a surge in 1968 (DDR: 9.1%). The last data point itself seems to be responsible for the average relative frequency of attributive adjectives (6.4%), which is not reached by any other text.

Fig. 5: Total volume of all adjectives (attributive, post-nominal) for each constitution.

One possible interpretation of this increase rests on exogenous political factors, which are harder to formalize and therefore difficult to capture accurately. The most salient explanation, at least with the information at hand, is derived by the systemic description (layer **system**). As the constitution of 1968 is the only one both attached to and constitutive of a socialist unitary party state, it seems plausible that political considerations have had some kind of impact. In order to test whether the shift could be explained by other functional considerations, the following diagram (Fig. 6) plots the relative frequency of adjectives according to normative function by way of variable **type**. While there are numerous outliers in the case of the organizational paradigm, the distribution of adjectives in both basic rights and organizational norms remains constant. This seems to indicate that influence through political considerations seems to be the most fitting explanation, at least within the bounds of the available parameters.

Fig. 6: Boxplot showing relative frequency of adjectives according to normative type.

One feature that is prototypical for legal or administrative documents is morphological productivity. Since administrative practices are in part characterized by the constant creation and addition of new statutes, laws or ordinances, new linguistic material is either derived from previously existing material or created wholesale. Specifically, the former is common to legal practice (Vogel 2017: 297). This productivity

can similarly be observed within constitutional law and the documents contained within the konkorp-corpus. As outlined in Section 3.3.1., the determinative compounds often combine a head with a federally derived non-head noun. These compounds denote a wide range of stately institutions, ranging from laws to governmental bodies. Fig. 7 displays the distribution of both types of compounds (federal and non-federal), their respective base forms (i.e. their heads), as well as the volume of remaining nouns.

Fig. 7: Relative frequency of nouns and determinative compounds across constitutions.

Fig 7. shows that compounds based on federal instances of government outnumber their respective base forms, while the opposite is true for compounds based on preexisting material. Looking at the relative distributions within the individual constitutions, we can observe that determinative compounds make up around 25%-30% of all noun occurrences within the corpus (total: 26.4%), the only outliers being both constitutions of the German Democratic Republic, with compounds only making up around $\sim 25\%$ of all nouns. A possible explanation rests on the relative size of state territory and the resultingly diminished federal state. Additionally, the constitution of 1968 itself cements the GDR as a centralist state after its federal structure was abolished in 1958 (Korioth 2023: 405).

In addition to the morphological productivity across sub-corpora, it's possible to test for compound distribution dependent on other functional or situational variables. The bar diagram in Fig. 8 shows the relative frequency by type of norm. The specific type of compounds highlighted in the annotation occur significantly more within state organizational norms than in basic rights (30% vs. 20%). This is certainly owed to the fact that the compounds are used to describe and denote state bodies, institutions, laws, etc., which are primarily formulated within the organizational paradigm. This discrepancy in morphological productivity (as specified within the thesis) seems to indicate differences in textual production. Naturally, this should not be taken as evidence for the existence of parallel registers. Rather, it might point to underlying functional considerations of norm production.

Fig. 8: Relative frequency of compounds (as percentage of nouns) by normative type.

Since official documents are assumed to be products of distance, another feature of particular interest to the analysis of register is the relative frequency of connectors within the corpus. Optimally, distant text productions should show a tendency towards sentence integration via subordination (Ágel & Hennig 2006a: 29). Fig. 9 shows that over time the ratio of the conjunctive part-of-speech-tags remains constant, again, with the exception of the constitution of 1968 showing both a sharp rise in coordinating conjunctions (*und* 'and', *oder* 'or') and a small dip in subordinating

conjunctions (e.g. *soweit* ‘insofar as’, etc.). The consistency seems to suggest that standardization processes of a legal style have been in place since the very beginning, mirroring a possible professionalization of scientific text production (Odebrecht et al. 2017: 719). The shift with the constitution of 1968 could again be explained with recourse to its political system. Combined with the datapoints from the adjective analysis, these results could point to the emergence of a discreetly “real-socialist” style.

Fig. 9: Evolution of the use of conjunctive types across constitutions.

As an example of situational variation, the following diagram (Fig. 10) displays the distribution of truncated nominal elements based on assigned topic. The chart illustrates that truncation occurs most commonly in sections belonging to the state organizational genre. The most frequent occurrences can be found in the legislative, executive, administrative topics. The differences in distribution might be explained by a variety of factors. For one, it seems possible that truncated elements accumulate with the increase of administrative concepts and institutions. Since most truncated elements describe various types of laws or governmental bodies (e.g. *Post- und Telegraphenwesen* ‘postal and telegraph system’, Art. 6 Abs. 1 WRV), it seems reasonable to believe that truncation is influenced by processes of state formation (as denoted by the meta-variable **process**). Aggregating the data by the **process** variable contradicts this intuition with both “sui generis” state creation and state transition showing

similar distributions (*Building*: 1.3%; *Transition*: 1.1%). Perhaps the process variable isn't accurate enough of a parametrization of legal continuities across state projects, failing to document the integration or shedding of previous administrative vernacular. It is also possible that the use of truncation changes based on diachronic change in language use.

Fig. 10: Frequency distribution of truncated elements according to assigned topics of sections.

A central aspect of this research program is the annotation of norms by their respective form. This type of annotation was achieved by parametrization of norms into either a *constitutive* or *prescriptive* type. Determining and categorizing individual phrase types corresponding to the forms was an integral part of the modelling process. Using specific search prompts within ANNIS allowed for the isolation of these regularly occurring phrases. After extracting the individual data frames from the search results, the lists were combined in Excel and reannotated according to phrase type. This secondary annotation is composed of: finite main verbs, finite auxiliaries in combination with participles (e.g. *sind abgeschafft* ‘are abolished’, only incl. lemmata *haben* ‘have’ and *sein* ‘be’), finite auxiliaries of the lemma *werden* ‘will’, finite modals denoting a conferral of rights or capabilities (*können* ‘can’), finite modals denoting obligations (*muss* ‘must’, *soll* ‘ought’, *darf (nicht)* ‘may (not)’), bare infinitives introduced by the *zu*-particle and infinitives morphologically integrating the *zu* ‘to’. These

correspond roughly, but not exclusively, to the normative notions of either establishment of facts (constitution/declaration/conferral of rights) (Wiener 2011: 40) or prescription of behaviors (limits, obligations) (Kniffka 2008: 169-170). As the diagram in Fig. 11 highlights, the finite main verb type (VVFIN) makes up circa half of the phrases across the corpora. This shows that there is a considerable degree of variation in verbal phrases, a possible indicator of deviation from previously established dimensional feature lists.

Fig. 11: Frequency distribution of verbal phrasal types across constitutions.

While Fig. 11 shows the distribution of frequencies across constitutions, Fig. 12 presents an aggregation by normative type. Since phrasal type somewhat conforms to normative form³⁹, we can see a considerable degree of variance. Finite verbs make up a significantly larger ratio of state organizational norms than of basic rights. This can be interpreted by recourse to the basic functions of state organizational norms, that is the establishment and description of government institutions and bodies. Basic rights, on the other hand, occur in multiple forms, either as basic conferrals of rights onto legal subjects or as limits upon the state's power to act. As with the analysis of compounds, this does not necessarily indicate different, parallel registers. It's entirely possible that the different ratios of phrasal types are a feature of discreet forms of text

³⁹ Which in turn can be annotated as either basic right or state organization.

production or legal styles stemming from the respective legal fields and traditions (Rockmore et al. 2018).

Fig. 12: Distribution of verbal phrasal types according to normative type.

A subset of the phrasal type is the recurring phrase of *haben das Recht* ‘have the right’. However, there are different ways of introducing phrases of this form. The most common form is the combination with a nominal phrase consisting of an article and a noun, e.g. *Der Kaiser hat die Pflicht und das Recht [...]* ‘The emperor has obligation and the right [...]’ (Art. 63 Abs. 3 DRV). There are, however, two other relatively common forms, those being the introduction by attributive indefinite pronoun (e.g. *Jeder Deutsche hat das Recht [...]* ‘Every German has the right [...]’) or substitutive indefinite pronoun (*Niemand hat das Recht [...]* ‘No one has the right [...]’), both of which are generalized quantifiers. Fig. 13 shows occurrences across individual documents. As we can see, nominal phrases introduced by article are most common in all constitutions. Since the constitution of 1871 doesn’t contain a dedicated section of basic rights (and barely any basic rights as it were), it makes sense that both indefinite phrase forms don’t occur at all. Additionally, the Grundgesetz is the only one including a “significant” share of the substitutive type (in total: four). One can interpret this increase as a precautionary measure to inhibit government overreach, with the substitutive being the most general (and therefore broad) form of determination, applying to the largest number of legal subjects.

Fig. 13. Distribution (raw numbers) of determiner type accompanying the phrase *X hat das Recht/die Pflicht*.

In addition to their distribution across documents, we can look at their occurrence by type. Fig. 14 shows both types of indefinite phrase occur almost exclusively within basic rights, while article-led phrases are most commonly found in organizational norms. This seems to supply evidence to the hypothesis that broader and less specifically targeted norms represent a feature of the basic rights paradigm. In this regard, the functional purview of the norm has an impact on its linguistic surface representation. Combined with insights gained from looking at the distribution of morphologically productive material and verbal phrases, we can point to a rudimentary collection of specific linguistic features that indicate variation in textual production based on exogenous factors and parameters.

Fig. 14: Relative distribution of determiner type according to normative type.

4.2. Quantitative results: analysis of endogenous features

Within the previous section, I have explored case studies analyzing both structural features of constitutions as well as the impact of situational-functional variables on the distribution of specific linguistic features. To stake out potential registers (whether single or parallel ones), one would need to mount a large-scale investigation into the distribution and relative frequencies of linguistic features in relation to each other. These distributions will then allow for recourse to endogenous feature sets. These would serve as the basis for establishing unique linguistic markers which define any potential register. In the next section, several diagrams will outline some of these relations, relying on different dimensions as outlined by Biber (1988, 2009), among others. The texts could, for example, be analyzed for their informational content, abstractedness, narrativity (Biber 2009: 831, 835) or distance (Ágel & Hennig 2006a: 17-18).

Immediately, it seems entirely implausible that the texts within the konkorp-corporus would exhibit markers of narratively structured texts. Features such as the use of personal pronouns or the prevalence of the past tense are extremely rare. Personal pronouns, for example, occur only 543 times in total and only add up to 0.77% of the total token size. And while the tense of verb forms wasn't explicitly annotated, the

manual annotation of the texts made it clear that most verbs occurred either in the present or future tenses (VVFİN, VAFİN *werden* ‘will’ + infinitive).

Since the corpus is designed in such a way as to test both initial hypotheses – a) the existence of a constitutional register, and b) the possible emergence of parallel registers – the following analyses aggregate the data along both axes: across the individual constitutions, as well as according to extralinguistic variables. The data was fetched and collected by using ANNIS to search for overlaps between parts-of-speech, all designated register variables and the titles of each text. Pivoting the data resulted in a matrix (cf. Appendix 9.2.) aggregating the frequency of pos-tags for every possible combinatory permeation of register variables, resulting in a total of 234 individual subtextual units⁴⁰. It should also be noted that data extraction is based on the paragraph layer, since the search was predicated on the overlap of the variables **direction**, **type** and **form**. While this distribution is useful, it results in a discrepancy between individual subtext-sizes. Seeing as some combinations only contain a low number of individual norms⁴¹ while others number in the multiple thousand tokens, the relative frequencies of each pos-tag have to be determined to inoculate ourselves against any distortions due to subset size. The search prompts that serve as the basis for the frequency tables can be viewed in the Appendix⁴².

Since the importance of the narrative dimension is ruled out, particular focus is placed on both distance and informational production. These will be examined first, before looking at featural distributions that could be idiosyncratic to the constitutional form. Discursively speaking, distance is often defined as depersonalized non-directed and primarily written textual production, often found in official documents. As mentioned before, constitutions both lack single producers and a clear secondary addressee. The modern constitutional form only exists in written form and is disseminated as such. The extremely low number of personal pronouns in the first and second person (with pronouns of the third person representing either anaphoric pronouns or the expletive use of *es* ‘it’) implies a lack of interactivity between producer and receiver in the conventional sense, creating a large amount of distance between the

⁴⁰ Combining all public-directed norms with both basic rights and organization, constitutive and prescriptive forms, etc.

⁴¹ The permeation *public/basic right/constitutive/family* in the Paulskirchenverfassung contains only two norms (§150, 151, Paulskirchenverfassung), for example.

⁴² The data itself is stored in a repository that is linked in the Appendix.

two⁴³. Ágel & Hennig (2006b: 61-63) outline some paradigmatic features of either proximity or distance during production. Important for this differentiation is the analysis of sentence structure. A look at the level of main clauses versus subordinate clauses can offer insights into the structural make-up. Fig. 15 shows the distribution of subordinate clauses (as part of all clauses) with the distribution of finite verbs (relative to total token size). There are multiple patterns that can be made out in this distribution. For one, there are a significant number of subunits that do not include any subordinate clauses at all. Otherwise, the relative frequency of subordinate clause collates around 20% to 50% with outliers reaching upwards of 80%, indicating a huge variance in the distribution of subordinate clauses. The outliers on the low end can be explained by the fact that there is a large degree of norms, both articles and paragraphs, which consist of single sentence utterances or multiple short main clauses that aren't coordinated (e.g. Art. 50 Abs.1 DDRV 1949). Looking at the distribution by direction also does not indicate any significant influence exerted by functional considerations. Perhaps, the large number of single-sentence utterances and wide range of frequencies of subordinate clauses points to a large meta-functional role of legal texts that isn't captured by the inventory introduced herein.

Fig. 15: Relative frequencies of subordinate clauses and finite verbs according to constitutional document.

⁴³ As indicated by the placement of official documents as maximally distant or planned productions (Biber 1988: 128).

In addition to notions of distance and proximity, we can draw on the dimension of informational vs. involved production (Biber 2009: 831-832). This dimension encompasses, among others, degrees of planning and coordination employed during production. One feature of informational production (as a negative loading feature of involved production) is the presence of attributive adjectives, whose distribution with finite verb forms are charted in Fig. 16. We can see that, while finite verb forms are relatively sparse (clustering between 5% and 7.5% of total token size), attributive adjectives cluster around and upwards of 75% with a large degree of adjectives appearing in 100% of instances (relative to all adjectives). These outliers are most likely explained by smaller textual divisions which potentially consist only of individual articles or paragraphs, e.g. *Niemand ist verpflichtet, seine religiösen Überzeugungen zu offenbaren* ‘No one is obliged to reveal their religious beliefs’ (Art. 126 Abs. 3 WRV).

Fig. 16: Relative frequencies of finite verbs (relative to total token size) and attributive adjectives according to constitutional document.

In a second step, the influence of functional variables should be tracked. Fig. 16 also shows the distribution of attributive adjectives by normative type. In this case, we can observe the distribution of types across the entire cluster. Interestingly, outliers in both directions, of increased volume of finite verbs and complete lack of attributive adjectives, are dominated by basic rights. We could posit that, since basic rights are often preoccupied with a conferral or granting of rights to non-state-affiliated legal

subjects, they exhibit a more involved form of production that is slightly less characteristic of state organizational matters.

Another hallmark feature of informational production is a high volume of nouns occurring in texts (Biber 2009: 831). This characteristic can also be observed in the corpus with nouns making up around a fourth of the total token volume. The diagram in Fig. 17 shows the ratio of nouns (to total token size) against the relative frequency of finite verbs (against other verb forms) with text units clustering between 20% and 30%, indicating a high degree of nominal phrases within the texts. Again, including other register variables like **form** in the aggregation reveals the similarity of norms of the corresponding types. The result for both adjective and nominal distributions point to empirical evidence that the constitutions of the konkorp-corpus could cautiously be described as informational productions, which through their qualities of nominal predominance, morphological productivity and presence of attributive adjectives are characteristic of a discernibly nominal style (Hennig 2020: 57).

Fig. 17: Relative frequencies of nouns and finite verbs (main) according to constitutional document and normative form.

There are some outliers, however, that seem to be unique to constitutional textual production. Both possibility modals, auxiliaries and indefinite pronouns exhibit positive loadings and are therefore features characteristic of involved productions (as opposed to informational production). While by any means not present in large

quantities in the corpus, modals cluster around 5-10% of all verb forms (Fig. 18). Of course, these include not only possibility modals but also obligatory modals. Their consistent presence still seems to be somewhat idiosyncratic. Testing for form reveals that modals are more likely to occur in a larger number of prescriptive text units, while their relative share in constitutive norms seems to be higher (Fig. 18). The diagram additionally shows the volume of federal determinative compounds (y_f) relative to all nouns, clustering most strongly between 10% and 20%. This cooccurrence can be understood as serving the agentive conceptualization of the state, bundling both its capacitive and obligational dimensions. Again, this could indicate different degrees of involvedness/informational production, with basic rights appearing slightly less “informational” in their surface representations.

Fig. 18: Relative frequencies of “federal” compounds and modal verbs according to constitutional document and normative form.

A similar conclusion is derived by looking at the distribution of indefinite pronouns, which occur with some regularity, but almost exclusively within the basic rights discourse (cf. Section 4.1.2.). Most of the subtextual units contain none of the indefinite pronouns, again pointing to a more informational style. Additionally, we can see that the prominence of indefinite pronouns, especially substitutive ones, rises with time, with later constitutions showing more occurrences than older ones (except for the constitution of 1849). This could be explained by its status as the original

modern German constitutional document, setting significant precedents (like constitutionally anchored basic rights charters) and enjoying an enduring influence, in particular with regard to other constitutions in the corpus (Korioth 2023: 388).

Nevertheless, these punctuated insights into distributions and clusters of linguistic features seem to confirm the initial intuition that constitutional documents are solidly informational productions, in line with most research on official documents. Still, there are some idiosyncrasies that surface when looking at both outliers from the statistical clusters and controlling for specific situational or functional variables. Particularly the distribution of finite auxiliaries by type is a good example of this form of control. Fig. 19 highlights the relative occurrence of finite auxiliaries (relative to other verb forms) by type, clearly showing that auxiliaries are contained more frequently in the basic rights discourse than the organizational one. The deltas between the type averages for each document vary between circa 8%-15%. This can be explained by the fact that auxiliaries encompass both dominant modes of basic rights, as either limitations (VAFIN + *zu*-infinitives) or creations of precedent (VAFIN + VVPP).

Fig. 19: Relative frequencies of finite auxiliaries (relative to other verb forms) according to constitutional document and normative type.

Paradigmatically, we can also use this example to show statistical testing of data from the corpus. To test the strength of this correlation, the data is modelled using the ANOVA method (Analysis of variance) in R. Modelling the impact of **type** on the distribution of finite auxiliaries results in a p-value of 0.000113, implying significant variation between the two groups. However, it's possible that some other covariate is influencing the test. This intuition is confirmed by testing for the residuals, which shows that the residuals don't conform to a normal distribution. Doing a multivariate ANOVA-test offers a more detailed picture, with only direction showing a significant variance (p-value < 0.0001). The p-value for type rises (now: <0.05), while form doesn't show any significance at all (p-value > 0.1). Doing a pairwise Tukey-HSD test on the covariance of finite auxiliaries with type and direction reveals that significant variation only occurs in the value-permeation of *staat:organisation* and *öffentlich:grundrecht* (p-value < 0.0001). Again, the data is not normally distributed, and neither should we expect it to. Since the design and annotation processes both relied heavily on categorization of functional variables by reference to linguistic material, the variables cannot be expected to be independent of the material. These issues will again be surfaced in Section 6.1.

Overall, the statistical analysis of distributional patterns of linguistic features across and within texts seems to underline some of the insights gained from the earlier case studies. While there are high degrees of variance with regards to features like subordinate clauses or compound distribution, the data tends to cluster even across individual constitutions (and to some extent when controlled for functional variables), suggesting some grammatical or stylistic cohesion. These results will next be viewed in light of the initial hypothesis laid out in Section 3.1.

5. Analysis

The research program was initially premised on two base hypotheses (Section 3.1.) Having collected and analyzed preliminary data on frequency patterns of broad structural, linguistic and functional features, how do the hypotheses hold up? In the following chapter, both hypotheses will be examined against the backdrop of the statistical analyses. In turn, possible interpretations of the results with recourse to political and legal-philosophical theories will be offered. These will touch upon the state in its different roles as sovereign, executor, intermediary, communicator, mediator, etc.

5.1. One single register or parallel registers?

5.1.1. Historical continuity and constitutional intertextuality

The central hypothesis at the base of this thesis is the emergence of a singular constitutional register, bundling different linguistic features across German constitutional documents, starting with the constitution of 1871 (but including the *Paulskirchenverfassung* of 1849). The analysis of the distribution of linguistic features seems to offer initial evidence for this claim. Analyzing the konkorp-corpus for its structural features shows that there is only slight variation across the 120-year timespan covered in the corpus. At a baseline, the basic structure of the constitutional form remained in place during that time. Every single constitution shares the same microstructural features, that is the division of norms into articles, paragraphs and sentences. Looking at macrostructural features, we can observe only slight variation of either sequencing, titling (adjusting for the change in eponymous nomenclature) or inclusion of prefaces/closing statements (which were annotated but ignored in this study). The biggest deviation can be found within the constitution of 1871 because of its lack of a dedicated section outlining basic rights. This consistency across structural features is also borne out on the level of norm size and length, even accounting for different text types or genres (basic rights, state organization). This consistency is again reflected with regards to the topical spectrum covered by the individual constitutions, highlighting the tripartite political theory of governmental branches (Stein and Frank 2010: 7-9) and the topical areas covered in the basic rights.

This consistency in both structure and theme seems to be carried onto the linguistic features to some degree. As shown in Section 4.1.2., there are several frequency clusters for key parts-of-speech such as adjectives, nouns and different verbal types. The relative distributions of adjectives and that of compounds remain stable across the individual constitutions, experiencing only slight fluctuations. In both cases, the only somewhat clear exception seems to be the constitution of the German Democratic Republic of 1968. Absent a more suitable parametrization of situational factors, the best explanation seems to make recourse to its political system as a socialist unitary state. Evidence for this suggestion can be gathered by consulting some of the legal-philosophical underpinnings of socialist state theory. The socialist legal theorists Pashukanis and Nazarenko point to the differing conception of a socialist legal project, notably its deviation from other constitutional forms by reference to political-historical theories such as historical materialism (Paschukanis 2017: 147) or class struggle

as source of legal meaning making (Nazarenko 1974: 45), which inform not only the surface representations of the normative content but also its political configuration. This can be seen most clearly in the preamble to the 1968 constitution, which more closely resembles a contemporaneous political tract (referencing U.S. imperialism and the division of Germany, Präambel DDRV 1968) than abstract-general legal formulations. Nevertheless, the constitutions remain strikingly similar in production across most features. This similarity could serve as basis for the existence of a discreet constitutional style, if not register. A nominal and informational style, which is still characterized by a somewhat balanced range of verbal types, from finites to a significant number of modals, *zu*-infinitives and high morphological productivity. On the other hand, a sentence structure that is defined by both large clusters of aggregation and single-sentence utterings, as well as significant degrees of subordination.

The question then shifts to how any such register comes about? One possible explanation could be based on the shared qualities of productive settings. Despite the inclusion of variables for political systematizations and transformations, information about the setting of the productions is occluded for the most part. Still, the consistency across both presentation and content can reasonably be argued to be the result of elite and academic discourse (Huber 1975: 90). While there were of course significant changes in the make-up of Germany's elite cadres over the decades, the increasing professionalization of academia (and the legal sciences) with the onset and progress of the industrial revolution in the 19th century ensured the formalization of both scientific and administrative practices (Wheatley 2023: 144). The democratization of these state projects produced crops of lawmakers from the nascent industrial bourgeoisie (as well as aristocratic remnants), while jurist scholars started producing systematized theories of state craft and lawmaking, such as Georg Jellinek (Kersten 2000: 74-75). Additionally, all constitutions (up until 1968) share the adherence to a positivist interpretation⁴⁴ of law to some degree, forgoing overt reference to states of natural law. Successive generations of legal scholars, lawyers and lawmakers were working within the bounds of distinct constitutional frameworks that, in turn, influenced the production of new constitutional documents when they became necessary after political turnovers (Wheatley 2023: 245-246).

⁴⁴ Legal positivism, as the notion the law describing a normative legal system whose source of legitimation is immanent to itself, i.e. the force of the law is derived only from its elements within the system (without recourse to natural states or morality) (Kelsen 1928: 132-133, 141).

5.1.2. Parallel registers and legal traditions

The second hypothesis revolves around the possible emergence of parallel registers, echoing the work of (Egbert & Mahlberg 2020) and owing its plausibility to the two discreet strands of legal areas (basic rights and state organization) that are combined in the modern constitutional paradigm (with the exception of the 1871 constitution). The question of whether modern constitutions are made up of different registers doesn't produce as much clear evidence as was the case for the base hypothesis. Frequency distributions by functional variables showed small clusters and tendencies, but the effects seem more tenuous while variance is significantly higher. The most striking deviation from total-constitutional clustering can be seen in more specific and niche (i.e. less frequent) features. The analysis of verb types or verbal/nominal phrase distribution shows some discrepancy when considering the functional horizon of norms (determined by the layers **type** and **form**). Finite auxiliary forms occur more often in basic rights than they do in organizational statutes, most likely due to the obligational qualities of many fundamental rights. Contrary to this tendency, the distribution of morphological productivity of compounds shows the opposite trend, concentrating within subtextual units containing state-directed organizational norms, with less of an effect induced by normative form. Since the effects on these features are relatively small (and seem to be limited to specific forms), it would perhaps be more apt to speak of different styles (Carlson, Livermore & Rockmore 2015), as opposed to wholesale parallel registers. These nevertheless seem to be influenced by the situational and functional variables ascribed to the normative layer. As such, they might represent byproducts of variation because based on the state's main constitutional functionalities. In this regard, the results seem to indicate that intra-constitutional similarities are products of productive settings while inter-textual variation can be linked to the functional horizon of the productive unit. Some of these different roles will be briefly touched upon in the following section.

5.2. The state as communicator, intermediary and executor of state power

In the extant legal-philosophical literature, there are many theories about the exact nature of state power. In Section 2.3.2., I have outlined the different strands of normative theories that influenced the formalization process of annotation parameters. The central split at the heart of normative construction can be summarized by different

modal modes, often evoked by the split into norms establishing facts (Wiener 2011: 41-42) and those prescribing types of behavior (Wehr 2005: 34-35). In the history of legal philosophy, this dichotomy is captured by the opposition of *Is* vs. *Ought* (Kelsen 1928: 75-77). This framework can then be adapted to the functional inventory of the roles inhabited by states. On the one hand, the abstract state takes on the role of communicator and intermediary (of its several institutions and bodies), outlining the basic precepts of state constitution and organization (Lepsius 2019: 10-11). The notion of statutory fact production is most directly expressed by the variable *form* and its concomitant features like the occurrence of declarative sentence types characterized by finite main verbs or finite auxiliaries like *werden* ‘will’, for example. The state as producer of facts can be likened to the historical explication regarding secondary types of rules (Hart 2012: 95-96), which are not occupied with the punitive exercise of state power but rather the generation of stability. In this sense, the state acts as rule maker and benefactor⁴⁵. In Hart’s conception of legal systems, this benefactory dimension to law can of course only be achieved by the interaction of primary and secondary rules (Hart 2012: 101). Thus, legitimacy is only established by repeated use and imposition of sanctions as response to the violation of rules (Pawlik 2017: 61; Núñez 2019: 137-138). This obligational quality expressed by the Ought-ness of norms serves as complement to constitutive norms, which set the base for sanctions in the first place. Here, the state acts as executor of state power. It should be noted that this function is not only reserved for punitive activity enacted upon the state’s legal subjects. On the contrary, to fulfill its role as guarantor of rights and privileges, the state wields state power against its legal subjects (including itself) by way of sanction, expression of responsibility and obligation, and the conscious fragmentation of power through hierarchization into different branches and instances (Kelsen 1928: 82-83). Obligational norms are also expressed using finite verb auxiliaries like *werden* ‘will’ or *haben* ‘have’ in combination with *zu*-infinitives. The strictest form of obligational norms is characterized by deontic modals like *muss* ‘must’, *darf (nicht)* ‘may (not)’, *soll* ‘ought’. Here, the state describes and outlines limits upon its ability to act in certain ways, based on a variety of factors like democratic containment or conditionalization. The latter can also be observed more directly within individual constitutions. In the 1949 constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany, for example, we can observe recurring use of the subordinate connector *soweit* ‘insofar as’ as introduction to subordinate clauses containing conditions on the realization of norms, e.g.

⁴⁵ In this case as benefactor of constitutionally protected rights.

(36) Art. 30 Die Ausübung der staatlichen Befugnisse und die Erfüllung der staatlichen Aufgaben ist Sache der Länder, soweit dieses Grundgesetz keine andere Regelung trifft oder zulässt.

Art. 30 Except as otherwise provided or permitted by this Basic Law, the exercise of state powers and the discharge of state functions is a matter for the *Länder*.

(Art. 30 GG)

This short review of different legal theories hopefully elucidated how the functional roles of the state have an impact on its linguistic representation in constitutions. While the early evidence provided in Section 4.1.2. doesn't seem to indicate strong functional influence on feature distribution, some trends can nevertheless be observed through the use of the parametrizations, thereby at least partly achieving the main goals set out in the beginning of this thesis.

6. Problems and critical evaluation

In this last section of the thesis, some problems that are inherent to research projects of this type will be discussed. These include the design of the corpus as well as limits encountered during its construction. These critical evaluations will then be followed by a short summary of ideas on how to combat or ameliorate these issues.

6.1. Problems of circular study and annotation design

Perhaps the paramount problem encountered during any register study requiring the processing and annotation of large amounts of data can be described as the problem of circularity. Since there are obvious indicators for operationalizing communicative and discursive spaces, the formalization will have to be done in view of the underlying text documents. This poses a problem, however. How do we determine whether a certain norm belongs to one group or the other? How does one derive appropriate values for **genre** or **topic** markers without prior familiarization with the text? While the annotation of the structural layers is sound⁴⁶, the situational-functional variables (**direction**, **type**, **form**, **genre**, **topic**, as well as **system** and **process**) had to be derived through a combination of previewing the textual data and close readings of

⁴⁶ Seeing as it's based on both superficial markers within the text like chapter titles and numeration.

literature in the relevant fields of legal linguistics, constitutional law and historical science. Determining whether any given norm belonged to either the constitutive or prescriptive paradigm then had to be derived by consulting normative theories in concert with survey of the data at hand. This potentially poses a problem: picking up on a set of linguistic markers apparent in a hypothetical variable, basing the decision regarding its categorization on this impression and then extrapolating a statistical relation between linguistic feature and communicative situation afterwards (Biber et al. 2020: 585-586). This mistake then must be remedied by modifying the annotation category, discarding it, or reducing its influence by including more material. One safeguard against this fallacy in the present case is the employment of the tripartite approach, annotating the level of the norm with not only its form (as communicative goal), but also its basic legal function and direction. Balancing these three factors hopefully inoculates the corpus against some of the biases otherwise present during the annotation and reviewing process. Another helpful preventive measure would have been the inclusion of some measure of standardization with regards to the annotation process, best exemplified by the idea of *inner-annotator-agreement* as is common in the corpus linguistic discipline. Employing 1-3 additional annotators (preferably from the realm of constitutional law) and measuring the individual annotation results against each other and calculating average annotation scores would have better informed final decision making. Due to the scope of this project, this was sadly infeasible. Reviewing the annotations in a more coordinated context and according to these best practices might prove prudent.

Compacting these issues is an additional problem of ambiguity. Even if circularity in annotation could be completely avoided, there remains some uncertainty over the functional and situational categories derived from more theoretical spaces in other disciplines. While I hope to have made clear my reasons for choosing and setting the situational-functional variables as they are, it is obvious that modelling communicative spaces on theories from social and jurisprudential science leaves open spaces for contention. This is best illustrated by reference to either the **form** or the **topic** layer. While both parameters are based on ideas and notions borrowed from other theories, their application within the context of large corpora and linguistic material is often not binary (as either true or false). Choices made under the constraints outlined in the annotation guidelines can be contested, especially with formalizations based on legal-philosophical explications. Sometimes, a norm can exhibit both constitutive and prescriptive content (e.g. prohibition of special courts, Art. 101 Abs. 1 GG). Most likely, this doesn't occur often enough to justify introducing a new separate value for the

variable, however. I will term this deficiency as a *cost of abstraction* resulting from transposition of categories from one scientific paradigm to another⁴⁷. This cost of abstraction will further be expanded upon in the next section.

6.2. Corpus design and loss of specificity

Since formalizing contextual information necessarily incurs a cost of abstraction, this cannot be avoided. Nevertheless, there were multiple alternative annotation schemes that could have been derived and used, in particular regarding the situational-functional parameters. The academic literature on constitutional law offers multiple ways of categorizing, e.g. communicative functions or topicality (Wendel et al. 2022). Some of those issues will be raised in the following sections, exploring counter strategies to prevent the specificity gap encountered here.

6.2.1. Additional functional annotations

One counter to prevent costs of abstraction is the expansion of the corpus in its current form. This would be achieved by iteratively, albeit very slowly, adding more specific layers of annotations. Particularly, the functional space can be supplemented by more granular variables. By adhering more strictly to jurisprudential commentary on constitutional law, one could introduce a plethora of new functional values. Since there exists a close relationship between the function of specific norms and their linguistic representations, an annotation on the sentential layer becomes possible, defining concrete functional values for each sentence contained within individual norms. For example, there are sentences that delineate limitations of norms, thereby inhibiting rights or state power. These are commonly referred to as *Schranken* ‘limits’ (Stein and Frank 2010: 240), while *Gesetzesvorbehalte* ‘reservation of statutory powers’ see the state reserve itself the right to limit basic rights (Manssen 2024: 65). Annotating these values would dramatically increase the fidelity of the corpus and reflect jurisprudential practice in a very direct fashion. This presents a problem, however. A sentential annotation of second- or third-order functions would drastically increase not only the workload and need of resources of such a research program, but also its difficulty by several magnitudes. Such an extensive research project would necessitate degrees of expertise which can only be attained after prolonged study of the relevant disciplines

⁴⁷ In this case from constitutional law, historical science and political theory to register linguistics.

themselves. Since most of the commentary outlining these specific functions exist almost exclusively for the constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany, one would still need to commit to some degree of extrapolation and formalization of contextual information for older documents. Furthermore, even an annotation scheme closer to jurisprudential categorization would still engender difficulties during the annotation process. Categories in the discipline aren't necessarily used in a uniform fashion, leaving room disagreement and contestation. Nevertheless, such an extensive project would offer fertile ground for deep register analysis.⁴⁸

6.2.2. Additional thematic annotations

Besides a more accurate functional annotation, the corpus could also be amended to include a broader breadth of thematic or topical annotations. Reasoning out and determining topical cluster has long been a mainstay of legal linguistics, even within the specific realm of constitutional law. Livermore et al. (2017) and Rockmore et al. (2018) have undertaken such topical modelling within the context of both the American constitution⁴⁹ as well global constitutions worldwide. Of course, all of these research projects share common aspects in their methodology, mostly relying on computational methods and the processing of incredibly large amounts of data. Committing to the manual annotation of projects of such scale would be completely infeasible. Since the scope of the current corpus is relatively limited, a more spread-out annotation of topicality or theme seems possible.

As with potential annotations of higher-order legal functions, the jurisprudential literature on constitutional law offers potential avenues for building upon existing variables. While the variables of **type** and **topic** are represented in the current iteration of the corpus, both are limited in their application: in the first instance to only two values (either as basic right or state organization), while the latter serves to collect sets of norms under the umbrella of broad topical ascriptions. Within the scope of this project, it made sense to limit the range of the annotation to general variables. Consulting either modern constitutional commentary or state law theories opens the space of possibilities. Stein & Frank (2010), for example, divide the basic rights into six

⁴⁸ Fidelity can also be increased by including more detailed linguistic annotations. In particular, marking discursive features as annotated by corpora like the *Potsdamer Kommentarkorpus* (Stede 2016). Conceivable would be the annotation of dependency relationships like antecedence which is common within the constitutional documents.

⁴⁹ In particular in its application via the Supreme Court of the United States of America.

separate categories, e.g. *Freiheitsrechte* ‘rights of freedom’, *Gleichheitsrechte* ‘rights of equality’, etc. (2010: 213). Alternatively, there are foundational types of rights outlined in the theory of subjective rights by Georg Jellinek in 1892. These include basic types of rights like rights to defense (*Abwehrrechte*), rights of participation (*Teilhaberechte*), rights to service (*Leistungsrechte*) (Jellinek 1892: 82-87). State organizational norms themselves could be subdivided into more specific values. They could be either described as imbuing *functional* or *institutional* content (Stein & Frank 2010: 5-7). In the preliminary steps of this research project, such a widespread program was attempted, as illustrated by Fig. 20:

Artikel	Absatz	Satz	R_form	R_funk	R_zweck	Adr	Adr_s	R_richt	Teil	
6	1	1	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	ehe und famil	staat-öffent	grund	
		2	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	eltern	staat-öffent	grund	
	2	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	staatliche ge	staat-staat	grund		
		1	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	gesetze	staat-staat	grund	
		1	mat	grund	soz	jedermann	mutter	staat-öffent	grund	
7	1	1	mat	grund	gleich	jedermann	uneheliche ki	staat-öffent	grund	
		1	mat	grund	inst	staat	staat	staat-staat	grund	
	2	1	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	die erziehung	staat-öffent	grund	
		1	mat	grund	inst	staat	öffentlichen s	staat-öffent	grund	
		2	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	religionsgem	staat-öffent	grund	
	3	3	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	lehrer	staat-öffent	grund	
		4	1	mat	grund	freiheit	jedermann	recht zur einri	staat-öffent	grund
			2	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	staat	staat-staat	grund
		3	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	staat	staat-staat	grund	
			4	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	genehmigung	staat-staat	grund
		5	1	mat	grund	freiheit	staat	eine private v	staat-staat	grund
6	1	mat	grund	inst	staat	vorschulen	staat-staat	grund		

Fig. 20: Rudimentary test annotation of the Grundgesetz (Art. 6, 7) using more granular functional categories including type of law (**R_form**, *Rechtsform*), specific goal (**R_zweck**, *Rechtszweck*) and formalizations of address.

However, the annotation suffered from many of the same problems as the hypothetical functional annotations proposed above. The method is constrained by ambiguity in deciding clear boundaries and the necessity of extrapolation to historical texts⁵⁰. Still, a project aiming to include both higher-order functional and topical annotations could offer a more definite insight into functional variation of language use within the constitutional paradigm. One way of stripping down such a project would be the restriction to individual documents like the constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany, making full use of the extant literature and limited scope.

⁵⁰ Extrapolation is necessary because much of the literature pertains only to the constitution of the Federal Republic of Germany.

7. Conclusion: Building on the konkorp-corpus and its research program

Finally, I want to conclude this thesis by highlighting potential research programs that can be built on the architecture of the konkorp-corpus. Since the corpus (along with the annotation guidelines and data structures) will be made available in an open-source format after the submission of the thesis, I would hope that further work on the topic can be encouraged.

While concrete deficiencies have been highlighted in the previous section, there are certain advantages to the broader categorization and implementation of situational-functional factors. The most obvious advantage is the general applicability of the annotations scheme. Whereas more specific annotations might have more accurately captured discursive qualities, the general nature of the definitions for **directivity**, **type** and **form** allow for a relatively simple transfer of annotations onto other texts of this type⁵¹. As such, the annotation paradigm can be projected across different situational contexts, allowing for a variety of investigations into similar problem complexes. I want to focus on two specific applications: a comparative format extending beyond national boundaries and an extension of the historical nature of this project.

A comparative account of situational variation can be achieved by applying the basic situational-functional annotations to texts outside of the German constitutional framework. In this regard, the research proposal would follow those undertaken by Rockmore et al. (2018). In comparing a larger number of constitutive documents, the strength of the annotation program could be tested. Historical research highlights the influence both the American and French revolutionary constitutions exerted on the modern constitutional form (Scheuner 1978: 172), a development reflected in the aspirations of many nascent nation states in the second half of the 18th century, from Europe to the Americas to Asia.⁵² Another avenue would be the examination of constitutions of newly founded post-colonial states in Africa during the decolonization of the 60s, 70s and 80s, which often mirrored trends of the late 19th century and their erstwhile colonial hegemons, as noted by Natasha Wheatley (2023: 254). While modelling single registers for multiple language communities is an extremely difficult task, (Li et al. 2023) explores indicators that registers remain relatively stable across

⁵¹ I.e. constitutional or constitutive documents conditioning state power.

⁵² Albeit somewhat belatedly during the early 20th century, see chapter 7 of Anderson (2006)

languages, thereby at least serving some basis for such a cross-linguistic comparative research program.

The second proposed approach retains the centrality of the historical perspective, extending its reaches both into the past and future. Remaining within a singular “legal tradition”⁵³ would encourage the exploration of diachronic change and offer insight into historical lineages of legal development. Since the situational-functional variables are more abstract with regards to their relation to legal norms, they should theoretically be more readily applicable to previous historically contingent legal forms. The dual notion of the norm as either prescriptive or constitutive carries across different legal traditions and isn’t confined to the relatively modern framework of constitutions. This way, annotations of previous German founding documents (such as those described in Sections 2.3.1 and 3.2.1) should be rendered possible. Since they might include elements of other areas of law like criminal or civil law, an amendment of the annotation categories would be necessary⁵⁴. However, the problem of establishing cogent historical categories would remain. The difficulty of retroactively making judgements about historical communicative spaces logically increases with time, while simultaneously introducing more variance through diachronic change in language use. An inverted program would focus solely on the Grundgesetz, including annotations for the amendments since 1949. The smaller scale would afford not only ample space for more granular annotations but also the possibility of tracking changes in legal language within a single state system.

Overall, I hope to have made some small contributions to the field of constitutional linguistics. Constitutions, after all, are the lifeblood of states and their respective communities in many ways. It is for that reason that viewing constitutions from the vantage point of register (as conventionalized language use of and by these same communities) can be extremely illuminating. Exploring possible parametrizations of functional characteristics, presenting them in case studies and relating them back to theoretical underpinnings hopefully showed the possibilities of the research of register phenomena in the arena of the law. Of course, the work and results presented herein are inconclusive and highly explorative. Undertaking a serious analysis of constitutional register would necessitate the comparison with and demarcation from other legal text types like bills of law or other legislative (itemized) documents.

⁵³ In the broadest sense of the term, as the only real connection would be some kind of congruence of sovereign borders or language area.

⁵⁴ For example by introducing new value for the **type** variable.

Ultimately, constitutions seem to mirror the constitutive norm: creating the conditions by which enforcement can be enacted (and is legitimated) in the first place. Following the philosophical imaginary, constitutions perhaps resemble more closely Hegel's *Bürgerliche Gesellschaft* 'civil society' (Hegel 2021: 343), a premature stage in advance of the to-be-constituted state. This kind of stasis is then exemplified by the deferred *Verfassungskonvent* 'constitutional convent' outlined in the Grundgesetz (Art. 146 GG), informing the understanding of constitutions as the preconditional formulation of the state and anticipating its legal or social reality (Koselleck 2018: 18-20). Or to put it in the words of German philosopher Alexander Kluge:

Erst das Bier, dann das Brot. Die früheste Gerste wird gebraut, damit die Ich-Schranke, ja, die die Menschen voneinander trennt, so gesenkt werden kann, dass sie sich auf engem Raum in einer Versammlung nicht erschlagen, ja, sondern vertragen. Und das ist die Grundform der Verfassung.

First beer, then bread. The earliest barley was brewed to lower the ego-barrier separating people from one another to such a degree that, when gathered at close quarters, instead of bludgeoning each other they reconcile. And that is the fundamental form of the constitution. (Kluge 2019: 02:30)

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9. Appendix

9.1. Documentation

Document list:

Constitution of 1849

Title: Paulskirchenverfassung

Filename: 1849_DR

Token size: 9875

State: Deutsches Reich (German Empire)

Date (of ratification): 28.03.1849

Orig. place: Frankfurt

System: Constitutional monarchy

Process: State building

Signatories: Martin Eduard Simson; Carl Kirchgeßner; Friedrich Siegm. Jucho; Karl August Fetzer; Dr. Anton Riehl; Karl Biedermann; Gustav Robert v. Mahl Zahn; Mar Neumayr

Edition: First

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

Constitution of 1871

Title: Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs

Filename: 1871_DKR

Token size: 7671

State: Deutsches Kaiserreich (German Empire)

Date (of ratification): 16.04.1871

Orig. place: Berlin

System: Constitutional monarchy

Process: State transition

Signatories: Wilhelm I.; Otto v. Bismarck

Edition: First

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

Constitution of 1919

Title: Die Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs

Filename: 1919_WR

Token size: 11615

State: Deutsches Reich (German Empire, Weimar Republic)

Date (of ratification): 11.08.1919

Orig. place: Weimar

System: Parliamentary democracy

Process: State transition

Edition: First

Signatories: Friedrich Ebert; Gustav Bauer; Matthias Erzberger; Hermann Müller; Eduard David; Gustav Noske; Robert Schmidt; Alexander Schlicke; Johannes Giesberts; Wilhelm Mayer; Johannes Bell

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

Constitution of 1949 (FRG):

Title: Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland

Filename: 1949_BRD

Token size: 13289

State: Bundesrepublik Deutschland (Federal Republic of Germany)

Date (of ratification): 23.05.1949

Orig. place: Bonn

System: Parliamentary democracy, Federal republic

Process: State building

Signatories: Konrad Adenauer; Adolph Schönfelder; Hermann Schäfer

Edition: First

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

Constitution of 1949 (GDR)

Title: Die Verfassung der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik

Filename: 1949_DDR

Token size: 9357

State: Deutsche Demokratische Republik

Date (of ratification): 07.10.1949

Orig. place: Berlin

System: Parliamentary democracy, Federal republic

Process: State building

Signatories: Johannes Dieckmann

Edition: First

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

Constitution of 1968:

Title: Verfassung der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik

Filename: 1968_DDR

Token size: 8799

State: Deutsche Demokratische Republik

Date (of ratification): 06.04.1968

Orig. place: Berlin

System: Socialist unitary republic

Process: State transition

Signatories: Walter Ulbricht

Edition: First

Annotation layers: word, norm, pos, lemma, clause, list, comp, abr, section_1, section_2, article, paragraph, sent, dir, type, form, genre, topic

9.2. Data collection, data frames, markdown script

Data was collected, viewed and extracted through the corpus-viewing software ANNIS by korpling group at the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. The corpus files were converted to the graphANNIS-format and uploaded to a local instantiation of ANNIS. The data was extracted through targeted search prompts using regular expressions. The resulting data frames were imported into R and relevant categories aggregated. Relative frequencies were calculated for:

Features:	Normalizing factor:
Nouns	Relative to total number of tokens.
Personal pronouns	Relative to total number of tokens.
Verbal classes	Relative to total number of tokens and other verbal categories.
Adjective type	Relative to total number of adjectives and tokens.
Comp types	Relative to total number of comp-values and total number of nouns.
Connector type	Relative to total number of connectors.
Clause type	Relative to total number of clauses.
Truncated element	Relative to total number of nouns.

Due to the large number of files (corpus files, prompt lists, data frames) and the length of the markdown script, I have chosen to append them through an open-source repository. Included are the base corpus files (saved as .xlsx-files), the .toml-script for conversion into the graphANNIS-format, a .txt-file with all ANNIS-search prompts, as well as the frequency tables and matrices fetched from those prompts. All relevant data and scripts can be found at:

Zenodo/DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416979>

9.3. Tables, illustrations, images

<i>Title/# Sentences</i>	<i>Par 1</i>	<i>Par 2</i>	<i>Par 3</i>	<i>Par 4</i>	<i>Par 5</i>	<i>Par 6</i>	<i>Par 7</i>	<i>Par 8</i>
<i>PKV</i>	275	89	28	8	4	3	1	
<i>DRV</i>	114	51	25	14	5	2		
<i>WRV</i>	292	111	67	31	15	7	2	1
<i>GG</i>	222	138	88	44	15	9	3	
<i>DDRV49</i>	211	108	64	30	13	9	3	1
<i>DDRV68</i>	179	118	67	21	6	4	1	1
<i>Title/# Paragraphs</i>	<i>Par 1</i>	<i>Par 2</i>	<i>Par 3</i>	<i>Par 4</i>	<i>Par 5</i>	<i>Par 6</i>	<i>Par 7</i>	<i>Par 8</i>
<i>PKV</i>	197	77	25	8	4	3	1	
<i>DRV</i>	83	38	18	11	5	2		
<i>WRV</i>	181	83	45	21	11	6	2	1
<i>GG</i>	145	90	58	27	11	6	3	
<i>DDRV49</i>	144	88	49	20	12	6	3	1
<i>DDRV68</i>	108	76	42	14	5	3	1	1

Table 5: Total number of paragraphs per paragraph number (above) and total number of individual sentences per paragraph number (below).